

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

Deliverable D11.1

ECCCH's Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda

HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01

Horizon Innovation action

Responsible author: Emanuel DEMETRESCU (CNR)

Project start	1 June 2024
Project duration	60 months
Document Identifier	10.5281/zenodo.20447414

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

ECHOES is a project funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement n.101157364, with the support of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee n.10110142 & n.10110466.

Deliverable Information

Project Number	101157364	Acronym	ECHOES
Full title	European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science		
Project URL	https://www.echoes-ecch.eu/		
EU Project Officer	Christian WILK		

Deliverable	D11.1	Title	ECCCH’s Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
Work Package	WP11	Title	Long-term sustainability
Submission date	29/05/2026		
Lead Partner	CNR	Responsible author	Emanuel Demetrescu
Pages	pp 98.	Keywords	SRIA, ECCCH

Change log			
Date	Version	Author	Change
15/12/2025	v0.2.0	E. DEMETRESCU	Initial structure
16/02/26	v0.3.0	E. DEMETRESCU	Major restructuring based on first review cycle. Incorporated feedback from A. Roi and V. Virgili. Mission/Vision anchored to GA definitions; Value Proposition reframed; Priority Areas repositioned as closing section. Verbatim citation of the GA as a starting point for Mission Vision and Added Value of the ECCCH
21/03/26	v0.4.0	E. DEMETRESCU	Proposed Mission, Vision and Added Value statements based on Poznań workshop (March 2026). Restructured post-M/V sections as background linking to ECCCH capabilities and architecture. Added WP leader annotations throughout

			for collaborative enrichment. Addressed reviewer comments (K. Arnold, A. Roi). Aligned ECCCH/Data Space narrative
13/04/26	v0.5.0	E. DEMETRESCU	Consolidated version for internal review. Accepted all tracked changes from v0.4. Integrated PESTEL analysis summaries (Sez. 3.1–3.3) from T11.1.2. Integrated WP9 assessment framework (Principles → Objectives → KPIs). Updated Definitions section with WP4 vocabulary reference. Added EU regulatory bibliography (Data Act, AI Act, DGA, Open Data Directive). Updated Section 5.3 with forward references to D18.2 Business Plan. Compiled list of abbreviations.
08/05/26	v0.6.0	T. PARKOLA, C. SZTEINSZNAIDER	Internal review
15/05/26	v0.7.0	All authors	Implementation of reviewers’ feedback
28/05/26	v0.7.0	X. RODIER, D. KOTZINOS	Final proofreading
29/05/26	v0.8.0	L. CZECH	Final editing

Disclaimer: Views and opinions expressed in this document are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Authors and contributors

AUTHORS

Emanuel DEMETRESCU, CNR
Vania VIRGILI, E-RIHS (former CNR)
Arnaud ROI, DARIAH
Agiatis BENARDOU, DARIAH
Giuseppe ZOPPO, ENCATC (former CNR and E-RIHS)
Carla FIGUEIRA, ENCATC

CONTRIBUTORS

Kerstin ARNOLD, APEF
Carlos ANDUJAR, UPC
Francesca FRONTINI, CNR-ILC/CLARIN-IT
Julian RICHARDS, UoY-ADS
Paolo CIGNONI, CNR-ISTI
Sarah MIDDLE, UoY-ADS
Rémi PETITCOL, FSP
Elodie CAZENAVE, FSP
Charlotte GALLINI, FSP
Maria BOILE, ATHENA RC
Ginevra NICCOLUCCI, PRISMA
Anna PUHR, ONB
Elisabeth STADLINGER, ONB
Christoph STEINDL, ONB
Edward GRAY, DARIAH
Sorin HERMON, CyI
Xavier RODIER, CNRS
Léna CZECH, CNRS
Amalia SIATOU, E.C.C.O
Elis MARCAL, E.C.C.O.
Dimitris KOTZINOS, CNRS-CYU
Johan OOMEN, NISV
Harry VERWAYEN, Europeana

INTERNAL REVIEWERS

Tomasz PARKOLA, PCSS
Corinne SZTEINSZNAIDER, MCA

Abstract

This Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) articulates the strategic orientations emerging from the foresight exercise conducted through the methodology of Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal (PESTEL) dimensions under T11.1, integrated with extensive stakeholder consultation across the ECHOES consortium. It identifies three Priority Areas — Infrastructure and Interoperability, Communities and Capacity, and Sustainability and Value Creation — aligned with the Cultural Heritage Cloud’s phased development towards a permanent European infrastructure. The agenda identifies the enabling conditions for long-term sustainability — including governance, recognised as essential and addressed in coordination with WP10 (deliverable D10.2 on governance models), professional capacity building, legal clarity for data sharing and reuse, and alignment with the evolving EU policy landscape. The document is the outcome of the work undertaken under WP11 “Long-Term Sustainability”, task T11.1 “Sustaining the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH)’s excellence within and beyond Europe”.

Disclaimer: Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Abstract	2
Table of Contents	6
List of abbreviations	8
Definitions	11
Introduction	12
1. Vision and Mission	13
1.1 The ECCCH Vision.....	13
1.2 The ECCCH Mission.....	15
1.3 The Value Proposition of the Collaborative Cloud	16
2. Background of the SRIA	19
2.1 Cultural Heritage in a Digital Age	19
2.2 The European and International Context	19
2.2.1 EU Policy and Legal Frameworks	19
2.2.2 Key Initiatives and Infrastructures.....	20
2.3 Creating this SRIA	21
3. Strategic Context (PESTEL, Foresight)	21
3.1 Current State of Digital Cultural Heritage R&I.....	21
3.2 PESTEL Analysis: Key Findings	23
Political Factors	23
Economic Factors.....	24
Social Factors.....	24
Technological Factors.....	25
Environmental Factors	25
Legal, Ethical and Regulatory Factors.....	26
3.3 Foresight Analysis: Scenarios and Strategic Implications	26
4. Guiding Principles	28
5. Priority Areas	30

Priority Area A: Infrastructure and Interoperability.....	30
Priority Area B: Communities and Capacity	33
Priority Area C: Sustainability and Value Creation.....	36
6. Implementation: Instruments and SRIA Evolution	38
6.1 Implementation Instruments.....	38
6.2 The SRIA as a Living Document.....	39
6.3 Sister Projects as Strategic Partners.....	40
6.4 International Cooperation	42
7. Conclusions.....	43
Annexes.....	44
Annex A: Catalogue of European R&I Initiatives	45
A.1 Introduction – Scope of the document	45
A.2 The European Landscape of long-term initiatives	49
A.3 Emerging Projects and Technologies.....	67
A.4 Conclusion and Future Outlook	71
References.....	72
Annex B: PESTEL Analysis Detailed Findings and Foresight Analysis Methodology and Results.....	74
B.1. Introduction.....	74
B.2. Methodology.....	75
B.3 The Six PESTLE Dimensions.....	77
Annex C: Glossary.....	95
References	97

List of tables and figures

Figure 1. Growing Asset Value Through Community Contributions — illustrative diagram showing progressive (non-linear, sequentially dependent) value growth through Metadata Structuring → Knowledge Graph Integration → Community Contributions. The figure is not to..... 17

Table 1. Mapping of Guiding Principles to Value Proposition elements and Priority Areas (A = Infrastructure & Interoperability; B = Communities & Capacity; C = Sustainability & Value Creation)..... 29

Table 2. The four implementation instruments deployed across project, consortium, and post-project levels. 39

List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AISBL	Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif
API	Application Programming Interface
CC	Creative Commons
CH	Cultural Heritage
CIDOC	Comité International pour la Documentation
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Italian National Research Council)
CRM	Conceptual Reference Model
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DCH	Digital Cultural Heritage
DGA	Data Governance Act
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPC	Digital Preservation Coalition
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
ECHOES	European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science
EDIC	European Digital Infrastructure Consortium
EITF	ECCCH Integration Task Force
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums
HDTO	Heritage Digital Twin Ontology
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights

JPI	Joint Programming Initiative
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NDSA	National Digital Stewardship Alliance
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, Legal
R&I	Research and Innovation
RIHS	Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
SEP	Single Entry Point
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WP	Work Package

Definitions

Key terms used in this document follow the definitions established by the ECHOES project glossary, implemented within WP4 as a shared vocabulary for the entire project. The glossary is maintained as a SKOS-based controlled vocabulary and will be made publicly accessible through a persistent URI upon completion. In addition, the Annex C (Glossary) of this document provides a concise reference for the most frequently used terms.

Introduction

This Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) for the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) provides a roadmap to guide the development and long-term sustainability of Europe’s shared digital infrastructure for cultural heritage.

Building on the activities carried out under Work Package 11 “Long-Term Sustainability”, and in particular task T11.1 “Sustaining the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH)’s excellence within and beyond Europe”, implemented with the coordinated contribution of the ECHOES partners — including analysing the current state of R&I to identify challenges and future joint activities (coordinated by DARIAH), foresight analysis based on Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal (PESTEL) methodology for ECCCH’s development aligned with emerging trends and technologies (coordinated by CNR and E-RIHS), prioritising technical maintenance and key research areas to ensure ECCCH’s sustained cutting-edge position (coordinated by CNR), and establishing cooperation frameworks with non-EU relevant initiatives (coordinated by ENCATC) — the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) defines the strategic orientations for the long-term development of the ECCCH. It translates these activities into a coherent and forward-looking agenda, guiding future research, technological evolution and international positioning of the ECCCH. As a follow-up to the SRIA, and in cooperation with the governance framework established in WP10 “Cloud Governance”, efforts will be channelled into garnering support from EU and international policymakers for the SRIA (FSP), including through the advocacy of its results, priorities and orientations in relevant EU and international policy-making fora.

The infrastructure that the SRIA is designed to foster — the ECCCH — represents a paradigm shift in how cultural heritage data is created, shared, and valorised across Europe. Understanding its strategic scope requires clarifying its complementary — not competing — relationship with the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage. The Data Space, coordinated by the Europeana Foundation, serves as the public discovery infrastructure that democratises access to digitised cultural heritage assets through standardised cross-domain metadata (EDM), addressing professionals, citizens, and machines alike. The ECCCH, by contrast, functions as a specialised collaborative workspace where researchers and heritage professionals create new knowledge through Heritage Digital Twins, employing domain-specific, multi-layered metadata via the Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (HDTO). The two form a virtuous cycle: the Data Space feeds the Cloud with digitised assets, while the Cloud returns enriched metadata and new knowledge to the Data Space. Scientific and societal value emerges from this complementarity — from connection, co-creation, and the progressive enrichment of

shared digital heritage as a common good. The document opens by proposing consolidated Mission, Vision, and Added Value statements for the ECCCH, developed through a co-creation workshop with the ECHOES consortium.¹ To translate this vision into a structured strategic framework, the document is organised as follows.

This document presents:

- The strategic context and analytical foundations (PESTEL and Foresight Analysis)
- Five Guiding Principles for ECCCH development
- Three Priority Areas with associated Core Themes for research and innovation
- Implementation instruments and mechanisms for SRIA evolution

As Version 1.0, this SRIA establishes strategic orientations validated by the ECHOES Steering Committee. It is designed as a living document, with explicit mechanisms for integration of feedback from Sister Projects, established European Research Infrastructures and the broader cultural heritage community. The priorities identified here constitute the reference framework for the development of the ECCCH as it matures.

1. Vision and Mission

1.1 The ECCCH Vision

Vision Statement

By 2035, the ECCCH is a trusted, open, secure, and sustainable European infrastructure that overcomes the current fragmentation of cultural heritage data while actively mitigating the environmental footprint of its digital operations, enabling it to flow seamlessly across institutions, disciplines, and borders. It is a space where heritage professionals — from small local museums to major research centres — collaborate as equals, where Heritage Digital Twins grow in value through community contribution and semantic enrichment, and where the resulting Digital Commons serves as a public good for research, education, policy, and creative reuse. The Cloud is governed transparently under European jurisdiction, independent of commercial providers, and has become as essential to the cultural heritage sector as any foundational public service. It embodies the principle that Europe's shared cultural heritage,

¹ The Mission, Vision, and Added Value statements presented in this document were co-developed during a dedicated workshop at the ECHOES Annual Event in Poznań (18 March 2026), with over 40 participants from across the consortium. The workshop employed structured facilitation methods to elicit shared priorities and aspirations for the ECCCH.

and the knowledge derived from it, is a common good that must remain open, sovereign, and collectively stewarded.

Vision background:

The ECCCH vision encompasses the creation of a Digital Continuum—a seamless environment where digital heritage assets are not static files but living building blocks of knowledge that grow in value through community contribution, semantic enrichment, and scientific validation.

"The digital environment proposed by ECHOES will empower users to interact with, manipulate and enrich Digital Twins Objects, leading to new, jointly developed scientific knowledge. The ECCCH built by ECHOES is anchored in Open Access and Open Science principles. It encourages participation by all, cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools. In turn, this promotes inclusion and democratises access to knowledge and digital assets, understood as public goods by and for all."²

This vision encompasses three foundational concepts:

- **Digital Twins:** digital replicas of cultural heritage objects linked to all associated knowledge
- **Digital Ecosystem:** the socio-technical system of components, tools, and services
- **Digital Continuum:** the environment enabling manipulation of digital heritage assets with full traceability

Together, these concepts enable the emergence of **Digital Commons**—a new generation of semantically rich, collectively produced digital resources encompassing not only tangible heritage objects but also archival records, library collections, intangible cultural expressions, and born-digital assets.

The Grant Agreement (Part B, Key Impact Pathway, Section 2.1) further articulates a temporal dimension for this vision:

- *By the end of the project (~2030): "the SEP is established, and the communities that have been created and cultivated in ECHOES will ensure the active usage and upkeep of the ECCCH."*

² ECHOES Grant Agreement, Section 1.1 "ECHOES vision"

- *Within five years after the end of ECHOES (~2035): "new networks of collaboration in the CH community will have developed, with different foci and characteristics, bridging gaps in the community and empowering the whole CH sector with new approaches."*

- *Long-term: contributing to "the democratisation of scientific breakthrough thanks to high-quality multi-source data and knowledge-sharing in the field of CH" and "advancing the triple transformation of the CH sector (environmental, societal, digital)."*

The Mission, Vision and Value Proposition statements proposed above have been consolidated on the basis of the co-creation workshop held at the Poznań Annual Event (March 2026), where 40+ participants contributed to defining the ECCCH's strategic identity.

1.2 The ECCCH Mission

Mission Statement

The European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) exists so that Europe's cultural heritage professionals, researchers, and institutions can collaboratively create, preserve, enrich, and reuse digital knowledge about their shared heritage — overcoming the fragmentation that currently isolates data across institutions, bridging disciplines and borders, and ensuring that the outcomes of funded research are integrated, accessible, and reusable beyond the lifecycle of any single project. The ECCCH is an open, federated, community-driven digital ecosystem where tools, services, and knowledge are co-developed by and for the heritage sector, evolving continuously through community contribution and shared stewardship, with services and knowledge growing organically alongside the communities that use them.

ECCCH Community Mission

The ECCCH community brings together the diverse and often fragmented communities engaged in cultural heritage research, stewardship, documentation, conservation, interpretation, and digital innovation around shared Digital Commons. Its mission is to foster a federated, inclusive, and practice-based community in which actors collaborate across disciplines, sectors, and levels of digital maturity; contribute to the shaping of tools, services, and knowledge; and collectively build more open, interoperable, and sustainable ways of working with cultural heritage. The ECCCH community connects and strengthens the existing communities through shared experiences, shared infrastructures, shared purposes, and shared responsibility for the future development of the Cloud.

The Mission is grounded in a concrete architecture designed to serve it. The ECCCH delivers seven enabling capabilities that together make the Mission operational: (1) a user-friendly access layer providing a single entry point for all heritage professionals; (2) a growing catalogue of services for processing cultural heritage data across domains; (3) reliable infrastructure maintenance and operations ensuring long-term trust; (4) smooth and fair orchestration of user requests regardless of institutional size; (5) a common Knowledge Base with easy co-creation of and accession to Heritage Digital Twins; (6) integration of the latest AI technologies, lowering cost and knowledge barriers; and (7) a unified ecosystem meeting the diverse needs of the CH community by bringing everything together.

1.3 The Value Proposition of the Collaborative Cloud

The fundamental question addressed by this section is: *What value does the ECCCH bring to professionals, institutions, and the broader cultural heritage ecosystem—scientifically, technologically, and economically?*

The Mission and Vision of the ECCCH must be understood in terms of the value it brings to stakeholders across multiple dimensions:

- **Scientific value:** the capacity to enable new knowledge creation through cross-domain data integration, semantic interoperability, and collaborative interpretation—research outcomes that would be impossible with isolated datasets.
- **Technological value:** the ECCCH's ability to adapt in order to keep pace with constant technological developments, ensuring that tools, services, and standards remain at the forefront of heritage science, digital humanities, and the broader practice of conservation, preservation, and valorisation of cultural heritage, including public-facing services delivered by cultural heritage institutions.
- **Economic value:** the sustainability of the ecosystem itself, including viable business models, return on investment for participating institutions, and mechanisms ensuring long-term viability beyond project funding.
- **Community and synergy value:** the capacity to bring together diverse and historically fragmented cultural heritage communities — researchers, professionals, institutions, and citizens — into a shared environment where joining forces produces outcomes that no single actor could achieve in isolation, turning collaboration itself into a distinctive source of value.

The ECCCH’s distinctive contribution lies in addressing all three dimensions simultaneously. The value of digital heritage assets in the ECCCH is not static—it grows over time through structured enrichment. Starting from base assets (e.g., 3D scans, images), value increases as metadata is structured, as assets are integrated into knowledge graphs, and most significantly, as communities contribute their expertise. This creates network effects where each contribution multiplies the value of the entire ecosystem (see Figure 1; the figure is illustrative and not to scale — in practice, structured metadata is a prerequisite for knowledge-graph integration, so the two stages are sequentially dependent rather than independent growth curves).

Figure 1. Growing Asset Value Through Community Contributions — illustrative diagram showing progressive (non-linear, sequentially dependent) value growth through Metadata Structuring → Knowledge Graph Integration → Community Contributions. The figure is not to

The core elements of the ECCCH value proposition are derived from the seven enabling capabilities of the Mission (Section 1.2) and translate them into stakeholder-facing value:

- **Ontological Interoperability:** The ECCCH enables data fusion and knowledge extraction—otherwise impossible from isolated datasets—through the HDTO, which provides a common semantic backbone based on CIDOC CRM, without enforcing predefined schemas, to which participating datasets and ontologies align.
- **Legal Certainty:** A codified framework for data usage provides clear expectations for both scientific reuse and commercial valorisation, removing ambiguity that currently inhibits data sharing.
- **Deployment Flexibility:** Institutions can deploy ECCCH tools in-house alongside their own data, deciding what to federate with the broader ecosystem—preserving autonomy while enabling connection.

- **Unified Access and Persistent Identification:** A Single Entry Point (SEP) provides unified access to distributed services, while standardised URIs and persistent identifiers serve as a trusted source of truth for heritage assets across the ecosystem—reducing fragmentation and enhancing discoverability.
- **Competence Ecosystem:** Coordination with initiatives like the Competence Centre for 3D ensures a growing pool of professionals capable of leveraging the Cloud's capabilities.
- **Space for Business Model Innovation:** The ECCCH provides a trusted environment for developing sustainable, context-specific business models that create value for both public and private actors.

These elements converge into a distinctive value proposition that can be summarised as follows:

Added Value Statement

The ECCCH's distinctive added value is that it makes the whole greater than the sum of its parts. By providing a shared, federated framework for collaboration that institutions can join progressively — through tiered onboarding levels matched to their digital maturity, with low technical and contractual barriers to entry — the Cloud turns fragmented institutional efforts into a collective resource whose value grows with every contribution — through semantic enrichment, cross-domain data fusion, and community validation. It offers simplicity where complexity currently blocks action: a single trusted environment where heritage professionals can share data under clear legal terms, access interoperable tools without reinventing workflows, and ensure that their investments in digital transformation yield a societal impact larger than any one institution could achieve alone. The ECCCH can also contribute to the broader European discourse on the responsible use of digitalisation and AI for cultural heritage, supporting values of openness, sovereignty, and public good in how technological innovation is applied to the sector.

2. Background of the SRIA

2.1 Cultural Heritage in a Digital Age

Cultural heritage in Europe is undergoing a profound digital transformation. The proliferation of digitisation initiatives, advanced imaging technologies, and data-driven research methods has generated an unprecedented volume of digital cultural heritage assets. Yet this abundance has also revealed critical challenges: data remains fragmented across institutions, interoperability is limited, legal frameworks for reuse are unclear, and the long-term sustainability of digital resources is uncertain.

The European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) emerges as a response to these challenges, building upon the vision articulated in the ex-ante impact assessment conducted by the European Commission in preparation for the Collaborative Cloud initiative. More than a technological infrastructure, the ECCCH represents a new model for how cultural heritage professionals, researchers, and institutions can collaboratively create, enrich, and sustain digital representations of Europe's shared heritage.

2.2 The European and International Context

This SRIA is developed in alignment with key European policy frameworks and initiatives, which are presented below in two distinct categories: the regulatory and policy landscape that shapes the operating environment, and the key initiatives and infrastructures with which the ECCCH must interoperate.

2.2.1 EU Policy and Legal Frameworks

The ECCCH operates within a rapidly evolving EU regulatory landscape that directly shapes its design, governance, and data management practices (for a comprehensive analysis of the applicable EU policy and legal frameworks, see D10.2):

- Commission Recommendation (EU) 2021/1970 on a common European data space for cultural heritage
- The Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025–2027, particularly Cluster 2 (Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society)
- The Digital Europe Programme and European Data Strategy
- Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AI Act) and Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 (Data Act), together with the European Commission's AI Continent Action Plan (2025) and

its flagship initiatives — notably AI Factories, AI Gigafactories, and RAISE (Resource for AI Science in Europe) — which establish the broader infrastructure and policy environment for trustworthy AI in Europe

- The Data Governance Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/868) and the Open Data Directive (2019/1024)
- The Culture Compass (European Agenda for Culture) and its implications for digital cultural heritage

Two of the above instruments deserve particular attention. Commission Recommendation (EU) 2021/1970 establishes the policy foundation for a shared, interoperable digital ecosystem for European cultural heritage. It calls on Member States to accelerate the digitisation of cultural heritage assets, improve cross-border access to digital cultural resources, and promote the reuse of digitised content. The Recommendation provides the institutional rationale for both the Data Space and the ECCCH, framing them as complementary components of a broader European digital heritage infrastructure.

The Culture Compass (2025), the latest expression of the European Agenda for Culture, reaffirms culture as a strategic priority for the EU and calls for deeper integration of cultural heritage into digital transformation, green transition, and social cohesion policies. For the ECCCH, the Culture Compass reinforces the legitimacy of investing in digital infrastructure for heritage as a driver of innovation, education, and democratic participation. Its emphasis on cross-sectoral approaches and community engagement aligns directly with the ECCCH's vision of collaborative knowledge creation through Heritage Digital Twins.

2.2.2 Key Initiatives and Infrastructures

The ECCCH is situated within a rich ecosystem of European digital infrastructures and initiatives with which it must establish productive interoperability and complementarity:

- The Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage (coordinated by Europeana Foundation)
- The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and its federated infrastructure
- European Research Infrastructures: E-RIHS, DARIAH, CLARIN, ARIADNE
- The New European Bauhaus initiative

The SRIA also considers international frameworks including UNESCO conventions on cultural heritage, the Faro Convention, the UN Sustainable Development Goals, and emerging global standards for digital preservation and data governance.

2.3 Creating this SRIA

This SRIA results from a structured process combining top-down analysis with emerging bottom-up insights:

- Analysing the current state of R&I (internal report) – Research and innovation landscape for the ECCCH – Current state and outlook – Mapping of the R&I landscape (see under Task 11.1.1) (July 2024 – January 2025)
- Foresight exercise based on PESTEL analysis workshops engaging ECHOES partners (February-September 2025)
- Draft of the SRIA
- Revision based on inputs from ECHOES WPs.
- Consultation with the ECHOES project bodies, including Steering Committee, Technical etc.
- Ex-ante report on the European collaborative cloud for cultural heritage (European Commission, 2022a).

As Version 1.0 delivered at Month 24, this document acknowledges that important sources of bottom-up insight—particularly from Sister Projects—are not yet fully available. The SRIA therefore establishes mechanisms for structured integration of this feedback in subsequent versions.

3. Strategic Context (PESTEL, Foresight)

This section contains a synthetic extract of the PESTEL analysis reported in its entirety in the Annex B.

3.1 Current State of Digital Cultural Heritage R&I

Europe benefits from a rich and articulated landscape of Research Infrastructures and strategic initiatives in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) and beyond, several of which are directly relevant to cultural heritage through the provision of data, services, tools, and collaborative environments. Together, these initiatives form an important reference ecosystem for the ECCCH, as they already address key needs in digital cultural heritage, including interoperability, access, preservation, analysis, and reuse. Many of them are also directly involved in ECHOES and therefore represent both strategic partners and important building blocks for the future development of the ECCCH.

Despite these strengths, the landscape remains characterised by significant fragmentation: institutions of varying scales operate disparate systems with limited

interoperability, technical capacity is unevenly distributed across countries and sectors, and funding models remain predominantly project-based rather than supporting long-term infrastructure sustainability. At the same time, key macro-trends are reshaping the field, including the development of data spaces and federated infrastructure models, the increasing adoption of FAIR data principles, the emergence of AI-based processing and Digital Twins for heritage assets, and the growing importance of open science practices. These dynamics define both the challenges and the strategic opportunity that the ECCCH is designed to address.

Within this landscape, a first group is formed by major European Research Infrastructures, especially those on the ESFRI roadmap or established as ERICs, which provide mature organisational and technical frameworks for research communities. E-RIHS, which recently achieved ERIC status, is the main European RI dedicated to heritage science and provides access to facilities, expertise, and digital services, notably through DIGILAB. ARIADNE RI, established as an AISBL, is a mature digital infrastructure for archaeology and archaeological heritage, offering interoperable datasets and domain-specific services. CLARIN and DARIAH, both established ERICs, are central SSH infrastructures whose services are highly relevant to cultural heritage research, particularly for language resources, digital methods, and distributed scholarly collaboration. OPERAS complements this landscape through its role in open scholarly communication in the SSH domain.

At a broader level, EOSC provides the overarching European framework for open science, interoperability, and federated access to data and services across disciplines. Within this ecosystem, the former SSHOC project has evolved into the SSH Open Cluster, which continues to play an important role in structuring SSH resources and services, notably through the SSH Open Marketplace. OSCARS represents the current science-clusters project supporting the consolidation of cluster results and the uptake of FAIR and open science practices across the European research landscape. At national level, clusters of national infrastructures nodes such as H2IOSC can be seen as a partially analogous initiative, developing a federated infrastructure for the humanities and cultural heritage in Italy and connecting national nodes of major European SSH and heritage infrastructures.

A central role in the cultural heritage data ecosystem is played by Europeana Initiative and the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage, which provide a mature framework for aggregating, enriching, and making cultural heritage data accessible and reusable at European scale. In addition, initiatives such as 3D-4CH, RICHeS, GRAPHIA,

and CC3D further enrich the landscape through expertise in digital preservation, conservation science, AI, and 3D digitisation.

Within this ecosystem, the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage, coordinated by Europeana Foundation, represents a crucial parallel initiative focused on data aggregation and access at European scale. The ECCCH is designed to extend beyond this scope by providing collaborative tools, processing services, and a unified Knowledge Base that enable researchers, heritage professionals, and institutions to work with cultural heritage data in new ways. The emergence of cloud-based and federated infrastructure models represents a strategic opportunity to consolidate these distributed capabilities into a coordinated European infrastructure, and the ECCCH is uniquely positioned to serve as this integrative layer.

Beyond the cultural heritage domain, other relevant European data spaces are also emerging, notably the **Language Data Space** which will be integrated in the **ALT (Alliance for Language Technologies) EDIC**, which strengthen the European ecosystem for multilingual data, language technologies, and AI services. These developments are particularly pertinent for cultural heritage where language, text, speech, and multimodal resources constitute a major part of the digital knowledge base.

Further details on these infrastructures and initiatives, including their scope, maturity, legal status, and relation to cultural heritage data and services, are provided in Annex A. The emerging EU compute and data layer for AI — in particular the AI Factories network and the Datalab initiative — is also strategically relevant to the ECCCH as a potential provider of large-scale compute and curated data services for AI workloads on cultural heritage.

3.2 PESTEL Analysis: Key Findings

The PESTEL analysis conducted under Tasks 11.1.1 and 11.1.2 identified critical drivers shaping the ECCCH's strategic environment:

Political Factors

The political landscape for digital cultural heritage infrastructure is marked by heightened uncertainty and volatility. Digital infrastructures are increasingly framed as strategic assets for European digital and technological sovereignty within European policy frameworks. Cultural heritage is itself a strategic resource in this context: high-quality, representative, and unbiased heritage data — of the kind the ECCCH community is uniquely positioned to provide — is a foundational input for sovereign cutting-edge AI

developments in Europe, including large language and multimodal foundation models. Yet the current geopolitical climate — characterised by shifting alliances, rising defence expenditure, and competing fiscal demands — poses direct risks to Cluster 2 (Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society) funding within the next EU Framework Programme. The ECCCH must align strategically with broader EU narratives around digital autonomy and critical infrastructure protection, while navigating multi-level governance complexity across institutional, national, and supranational levels. Fiscal constraints at multiple governance levels present a compounding risk: public investment may be redirected away from cultural heritage initiatives toward defence, energy, and more immediately strategic digital sectors. The ongoing debate around Horizon Europe budget allocation for the 2028–2034 programming period, coupled with political instability in several Member States, makes proactive advocacy for cultural heritage R&I funding an urgent strategic priority. The central question remains whether cultural heritage digital infrastructure will be formally designated as critical infrastructure within European strategic frameworks — a recognition that would fundamentally alter its policy standing, funding prospects, and institutional resilience.

Economic Factors

Long-term uncertainty in public funding availability, coupled with increasing volatility and rising costs of digital services, creates a challenging sustainability context for large-scale digital infrastructure initiatives. The ECCCH must demonstrate measurable value and impact to justify continued investment in a competitive funding environment, particularly as competition for EU budgets in the 2028–2034 period intensifies. Central to economic viability are the interconnected challenges of preventing vendor lock-in, maintaining openness while ensuring commercial sustainability, and designing sustainability mechanisms from inception rather than retrofitting them. The strategic imperative is clear: the ECCCH must embed economic resilience through diversified funding models, transparent cost structures, and demonstrated return on investment to secure its long-term position within the European digital economy.

Social Factors

The European cultural heritage sector faces significant disparities in digital competencies and infrastructure readiness, with pronounced imbalances between large, well-resourced organisations and smaller institutions lacking comparable technical capacity. Societal expectations are shifting toward recognising digital cultural heritage as a public good, while professional roles within the sector evolve to require hybrid skill sets spanning heritage expertise, digital literacy, and data management. Building social trust

in digital cultural heritage infrastructure requires commitment to transparency, explainability—particularly regarding algorithmic decision-making and AI deployment—and inclusive design principles that acknowledge heterogeneous user communities. Capacity-building must therefore be positioned as a core service layer within the ECCCH ecosystem rather than as an optional supplementary function, ensuring that digital inclusion and institutional equity are foundational to the infrastructure’s social legitimacy.

Technological Factors

The technological landscape is undergoing rapid transformation driven by the acceleration of artificial intelligence and data-driven workflows, alongside a structural shift toward distributed and federated infrastructure models that enhance resilience and distributed agency. Technology choices are increasingly shaped by regulatory frameworks rather than purely technical merit, requiring the ECCCH to navigate a complex policy-technical interface while positioning itself as a potential driver of European standards in digital cultural heritage infrastructure. The design imperative is twofold: infrastructure architecture must be modular and adaptable to accommodate technological change over multi-decade timescales, while simultaneously prioritising energy efficiency and sustainable computing practices aligned with European climate commitments. The strategic opportunity lies in establishing the ECCCH as a testbed for sustainable, federated digital infrastructure that can influence technological norms across the broader European research and innovation ecosystem.

Environmental Factors

Climate-related hazards—including flooding, extreme heat events, and wildfires—pose an escalating threat to physical cultural heritage, while simultaneously increasing the strategic importance of robust digital preservation and access infrastructure. Increasing societal scrutiny of the digital sector’s carbon footprint and resource consumption necessitates that the ECCCH adopt measurable sustainability key performance indicators integrated into governance structures, moving beyond symbolic commitments to operational accountability. A critical challenge is ensuring transparency from infrastructure and service providers regarding environmental costs and impacts, enabling the ECCCH to maintain integrity in its sustainability claims throughout the supply chain. Strategic procurement practices that embed environmental criteria

represent both a governance obligation and an opportunity to drive market transformation toward genuinely sustainable digital infrastructure models.

Legal, Ethical and Regulatory Factors

The ECCCH operates within a fragmented legal landscape characterised by heterogeneous copyright and intellectual property regimes across EU member states, creating ongoing tension between open access aspirations and the legal constraints that govern cultural materials. The emerging AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689), the Data Act (Regulation (EU) 2023/2854), the Interoperable Europe Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/903), and evolving AI governance frameworks introduce additional complexity, requiring clarity on liability allocation, responsibility distribution, and compliance mechanisms within the ECCCH ecosystem and among its service providers. Legal interoperability—the capacity to manage rights, licensing, and intellectual property across jurisdictional boundaries—is not a peripheral concern but rather a foundational technical and governance requirement for meaningful cross-border collaboration and resource sharing. Trust, while closely related to legal clarity, entails distinct societal and technical dimensions — including provenance, transparency, and accountability in processing — and is treated as a separate guiding principle in Section 4. The infrastructure must therefore integrate robust licensing and rights management systems as core components, supported by transparent legal frameworks that balance institutional autonomy with ecosystem-wide governance principles.

3.3 Foresight Analysis: Scenarios and Strategic Implications

The foresight analysis, conducted within Task 11.1.2, reveals that the ECCCH emerges within a complex configuration of cross-cutting tensions that define its strategic challenges and opportunities. Primary among these is the tension between infrastructure openness—essential for public good characteristics and ecosystem participation—and commercial sustainability requirements that may incentivise proprietary models and vendor dependencies; this must be actively managed through transparent governance and diversified economic models. A second critical tension exists between rapid technological change, particularly in artificial intelligence and distributed systems, and the requirement for long-term stability and preservation integrity that cultural heritage stakeholders demand; this necessitates modular, adaptive architectures that balance innovation capacity with stability guarantees; it also requires systems whose underlying characteristics remain transparent/hidden to the users, so they can focus on and continue their workflows without requiring them to develop new knowledge and skills. Underlying both tensions is the fundamental challenge of

distributing digital competencies and governance agency across heterogeneous institutions while maintaining coherent, equitable infrastructure at European scale. The strategic outlook reflects an imperative for the ECCCH to position itself as a transformative initiative capable of addressing climate-critical heritage preservation, enabling genuine cross-border scientific collaboration, and establishing European leadership in sustainable, ethical digital infrastructure—but only through deliberate design that treats governance complexity, economic sustainability, and inclusive capacity-building as foundational rather than secondary considerations. For the full analysis, see Annex B.

4. Guiding Principles

The development of the ECCCH is guided by core principles that inform all strategic choices. Each principle is anchored in the Value Proposition (Section 1.3):

Interoperability by Design supports Ontological Interoperability and Unified Access; Legal Clarity supports the Legal Certainty value dimension; Trust supports the credibility of Unified Access and Persistent Identification; Subsidiarity and Flexibility supports Deployment Flexibility; Sustainability as Systemic Responsibility supports the economic, technological, and community value dimensions of the ECCCH; and Open Source as Ecosystem Foundation supports the Competence Ecosystem and Space for Business Model Innovation.

- **Interoperability by Design** — ensuring that all components enable interoperability across data, software, and services in heterogeneous heritage domains
- **Legal Clarity** — providing clear frameworks for data sharing, reuse, and traceability (provenance and chain-of-custody of data across the federated ecosystem)
- **Trust** — ensuring technological trust mechanisms including provenance tracking, transparency of processing, and accountability across the federated infrastructure
- **Subsidiarity and Flexibility** — respecting institutional autonomy while enabling connection
- **Sustainability as Systemic Responsibility** — recognising that the sustainability of the digital ecosystem is inseparable from that of the physical heritage it serves: long-term preservation of cultural assets depends on a resilient digital infrastructure, and the digital infrastructure draws its purpose and legitimacy from the heritage it documents and makes accessible. The ECCCH therefore addresses physical heritage, digital infrastructure, and environmental impact as a single, interdependent system.
- **Open Source as Ecosystem Foundation** — building on open tools that generate community value

These principles are operationalised through the Priority Areas detailed in Section 5.

To make these principles actionable beyond the ECHOES project lifecycle, each principle will be translated into operational objectives with associated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), following the logic: Principles → Objectives → KPIs. This approach is aligned with the framework proposed by the ESFRI Working Group on Monitoring and Evaluation for research infrastructures, which identifies objectives (such as enabling scientific

excellence, delivering education and training, and facilitating economic activity) and then associates measurable KPIs with those objectives. For example, the principle of “Interoperability by Design” leads to objectives such as increasing technical compatibility across institutions and improving cross-domain data integration and reuse; KPIs could then include the number of datasets and services compliant with the interoperability requirements set out in D6.2. The full assessment framework, including the evaluation of the ECCCH as a whole, is being developed in D9.1 (WP9).

Guiding Principle	Value Proposition supported	Priority Area
Interoperability by Design	Ontological Interoperability; Unified Access & Persistent Identification	A
Legal Clarity	Legal Certainty	C
Trust	Legal Certainty; Unified Access & Persistent Identification	A + B
Subsidiarity and Flexibility	Deployment Flexibility	B
Sustainability as Systemic Responsibility	Space for Business Model Innovation; Competence Ecosystem	C
Open Source as Ecosystem Foundation	Competence Ecosystem; Space for Business Model Innovation	A + C

Table 1. Mapping of Guiding Principles to Value Proposition elements and Priority Areas (A = Infrastructure & Interoperability; B = Communities & Capacity; C = Sustainability & Value Creation).

5. Priority Areas

Three Priority Areas structure the ECCCH's research and innovation agenda. Each operationalises the Guiding Principles of Section 4 through concrete research and innovation themes: Priority Area A (Infrastructure and Interoperability) primarily embodies Interoperability by Design and Open Source as Ecosystem Foundation; Priority Area B (Communities and Capacity) operationalises Subsidiarity and Flexibility and the social dimensions of Trust; and Priority Area C (Sustainability and Value Creation) addresses Sustainability as Systemic Responsibility and Legal Clarity. The Priority Areas are:

Priority Area A: Infrastructure and Interoperability

Developing the technical foundations for a federated, interoperable digital infrastructure for cultural heritage.

Core Theme A.1: Semantic Frameworks and Ontologies

The ECHOES project has demonstrated that semantic interoperability across cultural heritage domains is achievable through formal ontological frameworks. The HDTO, grounded in CIDOC CRM (ISO 21127:2023) and developed within WP7, provides a comprehensive model that captures not only heritage entities and their digital representations but also provenance, interpretative narratives, and knowledge-production workflows. Through dedicated classes such as Heritage Entity, Heritage Digital Twin, Study, and Heritage Declaration Event, the HDTO models the dynamic, socially-conferred nature of heritage value and the evolving relationship between real-world assets and their digital counterparts (D7.1). The ECHOES Data Strategy (D6.1) complements this by establishing a data lifecycle framework that traces heritage data across its successive stages — from raw instrumental acquisition, through processing and post-processing, to interpreted knowledge and long-term stewardship.

Future research and innovation must address several open challenges. First, while the HDTO is aligned with the SYNERGY principles for ontological interoperability (as detailed in D6.1 <https://synergy-heritage.eu/>), deeper investigation is needed into how domain-specific communities (archaeology, conservation science, musicology, intangible heritage) can adopt and extend these frameworks without sacrificing their methodological distinctiveness. Second, the transformation of heterogeneous legacy metadata schemas into HDTO-compliant structures remains resource-intensive, requiring advances in semi-automated mapping tools and validation frameworks. Third, mechanisms for governing semantic evolution require systematic development to

ensure that ontologies adapt as heritage research methods and disciplinary priorities evolve. The research priority is to establish sustainable pathways for semantic framework stewardship that balance standardisation with disciplinary autonomy, ensuring that interoperability frameworks remain relevant to diverse research communities while enabling long-term preservation and reuse of cultural heritage knowledge.

Core Theme A.2: Digital Asset Standards and Quality

The ECHOES Data Strategy (D6.1) establishes a comprehensive framework for each stage accompanied by explicit metadata, paradata, and provenance documentation. Case studies conducted within WP6 reveal the complexity of ensuring data quality, integrity, and long-term usability across heterogeneous acquisition methods and analytical techniques: existing systems often excel at storing structured data but fail to capture the dynamic, iterative processes that generated it, while preservation systems and collection management platforms operate in disconnected silos. The interoperability framework defined in D6.2 further specifies the technical requirements for data exchange and quality assurance across the federated ecosystem.

Strategic research must advance several dimensions of digital asset standardisation and quality assurance. Formal schemas and automated validation tools are needed to enforce quality metrics across the full data lifecycle, with particular emphasis on documenting both technical specifications (format, resolution, accuracy) and contextual quality (completeness, consistency, fitness-for-purpose). Research should develop standardised approaches to paradata capture and representation, documenting processing algorithms, operator decisions, and methodological rationales in a machine-actionable form that enables reproducibility and cross-institutional comparison. As heritage institutions contribute data at varying levels of maturity, frameworks are required that accommodate progressive enrichment and validation stages without mandating centralised quality gatekeeping. The innovation priority is to establish distributed, community-driven quality assurance mechanisms that embed FAIR principles into the creation and governance of digital heritage assets, enabling smaller and under-resourced institutions to participate while maintaining rigorous standards.

Core Theme A.3: Federation and Distributed Architecture

The ECHOES Integration Strategy (D3.1) articulates a vision of the ECCCH as a genuinely federated ecosystem: not a centralised repository, but a distributed network of institutional data nodes connected through common standards, shared semantic frameworks, and distributed querying mechanisms. Three progressive integration levels are defined: Level 1 (Tactical, with catalogue federation and centralised metadata

pointers to distributed data sources); Level 2 (Strategic, with semantic alignment via HDTO and unified APIs enabling hybrid federation); and Level 3 (Transformational, with federated compute, cross-node orchestration, and edge computing). The Integration Roadmap (D3.2) translates this vision into concrete implementation phases, detailing the technical milestones, governance requirements, and community engagement activities needed at each stage. This architecture is intentionally designed to preserve institutional autonomy while enabling collaborative knowledge creation around Digital Commons.

Substantial research gaps remain in implementing genuinely distributed, resilient heritage infrastructure. Current federated knowledge systems often lack unified querying mechanisms or rely on parallel named graphs within centralised repositories rather than true federation. Research priorities include: developing robust distributed consensus and query protocols that enable seamless cross-institutional discovery and analysis without requiring data centralisation; establishing governance frameworks and contractual mechanisms that clarify responsibilities for resource providers, institutional participants, and the central legal entity during the ECCCH transition from project to sustainable infrastructure; and advancing technical approaches to federated compute that allow algorithms to execute where data resides, minimising latency while respecting institutional security and intellectual property constraints. Federation approaches must also accommodate heterogeneous institutional contexts, from large national research infrastructures to small local heritage institutions with limited technical capacity.

Core Theme A.4: AI and Advanced Technologies

The ECHOES project recognises that artificial intelligence and machine learning are increasingly central to cultural heritage research, from automated transcription of historical documents to semantic enrichment of complex datasets and discovery of patterns across distributed collections. The Vertical Applications framework developed in WP8 (D8.1) demonstrates emerging use cases including automatic text recognition and transcription (VTL), spatial annotation of 3D and 2D representations (OCRA), and AI-assisted cataloguing and metadata enrichment (CIT). However, critical research gaps and ethical imperatives accompany AI integration in heritage science: models trained on biased historical records risk perpetuating gaps in documentation; automated systems generating metadata without explicit provenance chains obscure the distinction between observation and interpretation; and reliance on commercial AI services raises concerns about data sovereignty and long-term preservation. AI offers transformative opportunities for cultural heritage: data cleaning and normalisation at scale, automated inspection and condition assessment, intelligent curation and metadata enrichment, and advanced analytical capabilities that no single institution could develop alone. At the

same time, the ECCCH must engage with the emerging European framework for AI sovereignty and certification (AI Act, Regulation EU 2024/1689), positioning the Cloud as a context where AI tools are deployed responsibly, with full provenance tracking, and in alignment with European values. Open research questions remain around bias in models trained on historical records, the distinction between AI-generated and human-validated metadata, and the governance of AI services within a federated infrastructure.

Future research must address several dimensions of responsible AI integration. Rigorous investigation is needed into how machine learning models trained on cultural heritage data can be evaluated for bias, fairness, and representativeness, particularly regarding underrepresented heritage communities and non-Western cultural traditions. Frameworks are required that ensure explicit provenance and transparency when AI systems contribute to heritage knowledge production: the heritage record must document both the AI method employed and the human validation processes applied. Institutional capacity building is essential to enable heritage professionals to critically evaluate and responsibly deploy AI tools within their workflows. Research should also investigate approaches to federated and privacy-preserving machine learning that enable model training across distributed institutions without centralising sensitive cultural data. The innovation priority is to develop practical guidelines, shared benchmarks, and governance frameworks for AI integration in cultural heritage that maximise analytical power while maintaining scholarly integrity, data sovereignty, and alignment with European AI certification requirements.

Priority Area B: Communities and Capacity

Building the human, organizational, and cross-sectoral networks that enable effective use of the ECCCH — including capacity building within the Data Space framework and through Umbrella Organisations that connect local, national, and European heritage communities.

Core Theme B.1: Professional Development and Training

The ECHOES Consultation and WP4/WP5 engagement activities (D4.1) have identified a critical infrastructure-training nexus: cultural heritage professionals require integrated technical capacity building embedded within the Cloud infrastructure itself, rather than as a peripheral service. Evidence indicates that integrating new digital tools into existing professional workflows typically requires extended adaptation periods, with barriers including insufficient documentation, resistance to workflow disruption, and limited familiarity with coding-intensive tools. Strategic priorities must therefore shift from periodic external training programmes toward modular, adaptive capacity-building

mechanisms that embed training and support into the core Cloud architecture and service design, including user-centred documentation, peer mentoring systems, layered onboarding pathways for different skill levels, and iterative tool validation conducted alongside practitioners in their actual work contexts.

The cultural heritage sector comprises hybrid skill sets spanning heritage expertise, digital literacy, data stewardship, and interpretive authority. Training frameworks must acknowledge this diversity while moving beyond traditional disciplinary boundaries toward transversal competencies in data management, semantic modelling, and computational analysis. Strategies for sustainable capacity building must address cost barriers that prevent access to training resources and expert-led workshops, while establishing pathways for peer learning and community-generated expertise that leverage existing professional networks and umbrella organisations. The ECCCH requires comprehensive capacity-building policies that position training and knowledge transfer as foundational: modular training curricula tailored to different user profiles; a capacity-building service desk providing ongoing technical and methodological support; mechanisms for capturing and codifying tacit knowledge; and incentive structures that recognise the contribution of professionals who mentor peers and contribute to community documentation.

Core Theme B.2: Engagement Models

The ECHOES Integration Strategy (D3.1) establishes a multi-level framework for participation that accommodates the diversity of European cultural heritage organisations, from small independent practitioners to major research infrastructures. Level 1 (Basic Connectivity) enables individual institutions to contribute data and services without institutional restructuring; Level 2 (Semantic and Technical Integration) supports proactive alignment with ECCCH interoperability standards and resource provision; and Level 3 (Federated Ecosystem Participation) positions institutions as core infrastructure providers. This approach directly addresses the heterogeneous capacities identified in the WP4 Consultation (D4.1), where institutions range from those with dedicated data management teams and institutional authentication infrastructure to freelance professionals relying on personal commercial cloud services.

Evidence from WP3 and WP4 activities demonstrates that institutional adoption depends on technical solutions addressing both large-scale and small-scale constraints. For research-intensive institutions, the Cloud must function as an integrated extension of existing institutional systems, supporting single sign-on authentication, long-term archiving guarantees, and federated governance aligned with institutional mandates. For smaller organisations and independent professionals, barriers include cost, lack of

technical infrastructure, and limited capacity for data management workflows. The federated architecture defined in D3.1 responds to this tension by allowing data to reside in distributed nodes while enabling seamless discovery through the central Knowledge Base, preserving institutional sovereignty while delivering economies of scale. Strategic priorities include: establishing service-level agreements and sustainability frameworks that guarantee long-term commitment to smaller organisations; creating institutional onboarding pathways that transition resources through integration levels over time; and ensuring that governance decisions reflect the voices of diverse institutional profiles.

Core Theme B.3: Cross-Sectoral Collaboration

ECHOES consultation results (D4.1) reveal systemic fragmentation across the cultural heritage ecosystem, where research, creative industries, conservation professionals, and technology specialists operate in disciplinary and organisational silos despite sharing common data infrastructure needs. Barriers persist across multiple dimensions: limited adoption of common metadata standards and ontologies, absence of interoperable workflows linking fieldwork, documentation, analysis, and dissemination, and limited professional mobility and recognition across sectoral boundaries. The Heritage Digital Twin concept embedded in the ECHOES infrastructure provides a powerful integrative mechanism: by structuring cultural heritage assets as distributed, interconnected knowledge objects combining geometry, metadata, conservation records, and interpretive annotation, the Cloud enables researchers, conservators, curators, and technologists to contribute distinct expertise to shared enriched representations.

The ECCCH Integration Task Force (EITF) and WP3 collaborative research scenarios establish operational templates for cross-sectoral work: co-design workshops engaging archaeology, conservation science, heritage documentation, and computational specialists; shared semantic frameworks translating between disciplinary vocabularies; and transparent role definition allowing each sector to contribute according to its comparative advantage. The ECCCH must institutionalise cross-sectoral collaboration as a design principle rather than an incidental outcome, through sustained investment in: governance structures ensuring equitable representation from research, conservation, GLAM institutions, creative industries, and technology sectors; funded mechanisms for co-design and collaborative research that bring multi-sectoral teams together on real challenges; translation services enabling seamless data and knowledge exchange across disciplinary vocabularies; and career incentive structures recognising interdisciplinary contributions. Long-term sustainability depends on formalising cross-sectoral engagement within the ECCCH legal entity governance.

Priority Area C: Sustainability and Value Creation

This Priority Area addresses the strategic and operational dimensions of sustainability for the ECCCH — encompassing economic viability, legal frameworks for data valorisation, community governance models, and the long-term preservation of both digital and physical heritage. It integrates the institutional sustainability framework (governance trajectory, ESFRI positioning, long-term funding architecture) with the concrete mechanisms through which sustainability is enacted at the service and community level.

Core Theme C.1: Economic Models and Business Cases

Ensuring the long-term economic viability of the ECCCH requires a multi-layered approach to value creation and funding diversification. At the core of this theme lies the concept of the Heritage Digital Twin as a value generator: digital representations of cultural heritage objects and sites can serve as generators of value that contributes to the preservation of their physical counterparts, drawing on historical models of heritage stewardship where assets generate resources for their own maintenance. Sustainability also requires balancing open access with mechanisms for value capture through differentiated access models: non-commercial, educational, and research use should remain freely accessible, while commercial use above defined thresholds may involve contributions that support ecosystem sustainability, following freemium approaches proven in other digital commons. The connection between a digital asset and the physical heritage it represents — and the jurisdiction responsible for that heritage — provides a basis for territorial linkage models that connect digital value creation to physical heritage stewardship. The SRIA draws further inspiration from adjacent ecosystems: the creative industries (games, VFX, digital cinema) demonstrate how tool platforms build communities of users who both consume and produce content, generating network effects that sustain the ecosystem; the music and audio sector offers deep expertise in metadata standardisation and balancing open access with sustainable value creation; scientific publishing’s open access transformation provides insights on balancing openness with sustainability through preprint servers and evolving licensing models; geospatial data infrastructures demonstrate how standardisation through use and federated governance can sustain large-scale digital commons; and digital preservation communities (DPC, NDSA, Open Preservation Foundation) represent mature collective action models for shared infrastructure. These lessons will be further developed in the ECCCH Business Plan (D18.2, M57).

Core Theme C.2: Legal Frameworks for Data Valorisation

The legal dimension of sustainability encompasses three interconnected challenges. First, data access harmonisation: working toward consistent frameworks for cultural heritage data access across Member States, reducing barriers to cross-border collaboration and ensuring that legal fragmentation does not undermine the ECCCH’s federated architecture. Second, investment recognition and distinction: a critical challenge emerges from the current funding landscape where resources for digital heritage creation are increasing while funding for physical heritage maintenance and restoration is declining. Creating a digital replica does not equate to restoring the physical object; mechanisms must be designed where digital assets can generate value that flows back to physical preservation — complementing, not replacing, direct conservation investment. Third, ministerial coordination: addressing the fragmentation of competences across culture, research, and digital transformation ministries at both national and EU levels requires strategic advocacy to ensure that the ECCCH is recognised across all relevant policy domains. These orientations will be refined through coordination with WP10 (Governance) and the development of D18.1 (Open Innovation Strategy).

Core Theme C.3: Heritage Digital Twins and Long-Term Digital Preservation

This core theme addresses the interdependence of physical heritage, digital infrastructure, and the collaborative ecosystem. A distinctive feature of this SRIA is its recognition that ECCCH sustainability cannot be addressed in isolation: three dimensions must be considered together. The sustainability of physical cultural heritage: the primary purpose of digital cultural heritage is to serve the understanding, preservation, and valorisation of physical heritage, and any sustainability model must ultimately contribute to the conservation of the tangible and intangible heritage it represents. The sustainability of digital infrastructure: digital assets require ongoing curation, storage, and maintenance; the technical infrastructure must be designed for long-term viability, with clear responsibilities for preservation and update; as mandated in the Grant Agreement, this SRIA addresses long-term digital preservation as a core strategic concern — recognising that digital documentation must be preserved with the same commitment applied to physical heritage, particularly when digital records constitute the only surviving representation of lost or endangered assets. The sustainability of the collaborative ecosystem: beyond individual assets and infrastructure, the social and institutional ecosystem that creates, uses, and enriches ECCCH resources must be sustained through appropriate governance, incentives, and value circulation. Supporting the full lifecycle of digital heritage — from creation through scientific analysis to public communication and education — is essential to maintaining the virtuous cycle of knowledge production that underpins the ECCCH’s long-term value.

6. Implementation: Instruments and SRIA Evolution

6.1 Implementation Instruments

The ECCCH’s strategic orientations will be realised through four complementary types of instruments, each operating at a different level of the research and innovation ecosystem.

Funding instruments. The SRIA’s implementation depends on alignment with European and national funding mechanisms. At the European level, this means ensuring that ECCCH priorities are reflected in Horizon Europe Cluster 2 work programmes, the Digital Europe Programme, and the forthcoming calls under the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage. At the national level, it requires engagement with member-state funding agencies and the relevant national digital strategies (for culture, research, and the digital economy) to ensure that nationally funded digitisation, conservation, and research programmes recognise the ECCCH as an integration point. The SRIA does not itself allocate funding; it provides the strategic reference framework against which funding proposals—both by ECHOES and by the broader community—can demonstrate alignment with long-term European priorities.

Networking instruments. The ECCCH’s value lies in its capacity to connect heterogeneous communities. Networking instruments include formal coordination with European Research Infrastructures (E-RIH, DARIAH, CLARIN, ARIADNE), structured engagement with the EOSC ecosystem, and the ECCCH Integration Task Force (EITF) that coordinates Sister Project integration. Beyond the project consortium, the SRIA envisages outreach to professional heritage networks, museum associations, archival communities, and commercial archaeology practitioners—constituencies whose adoption is essential for the ECCCH’s long-term sustainability but who are not yet systematically represented in the governance structure.

Capacity building instruments. The digital transformation of cultural heritage practice requires investment in human capital. Capacity building instruments include training programmes developed by ECHOES WP15 and by Sister Projects (several of which are building dedicated training platforms), documentation and best-practice guides for ECCCH integration, and knowledge-exchange formats that facilitate transfer between projects operating in different heritage domains. A particular challenge is ensuring that

capacity building reaches smaller institutions and practitioners in countries with less-developed digital heritage infrastructure—a concern raised explicitly in the PESTEL analysis (Section 3.2, Social Factors).

Governance instruments. Strategic coherence across the ECCCH ecosystem requires governance mechanisms that operate at multiple levels. Within ECHOES, these include the Steering Committee validation process for strategic decisions, the coordination between WP10 (Governance), WP11 (SRIA), and WP18 (Sustainability). Beyond the project, the SRIA anticipates the need for a governance framework that can outlast ECHOES itself—one that provides decision-making structures for ontology evolution, API versioning, resource allocation, and the admission of new participants. The design of this post-project governance is developed within WP10 (Governance), in coordination with the sustainability framework defined in WP11 and the economic models in D18.2.

Instrument	Project (ECHOES)	Consortium	Post-project ecosystem
Funding	Cluster 2 / DEP alignment	Sister Project coordination	National strategies; post-2027 calls
Networking	ECCCH Integration Task Force (EITF)	E-RIHS, DARIAH, CLARIN, ARIADNE; EOSC	Heritage networks; museum & archive associations
Capacity building	WP15 training programmes	Sister Project training platforms	Practitioner networks; small institutions
Governance	Steering Committee; WP10 / WP11 / WP18	EITF coordination	ECCCH legal entity; ontology stewardship

Table 2. The four implementation instruments deployed across project, consortium, and post-project levels.

6.2 The SRIA as a Living Document

This SRIA is designed as a living document. As Version 1.0 delivered at Month 24, it establishes strategic orientations validated by the ECHOES Steering Committee while acknowledging that important sources of bottom-up insight—particularly from Sister Projects—are not yet fully available.

The SRIA therefore establishes mechanisms for structured integration of feedback in the project's ongoing activities, coordinated with other deliverables from WP11/WP18 that address complementary aspects of ECCCH sustainability:

D18.1 – Integrated Strategy for Multilevel Open Innovation (M48) Led by ENCATC. Strategic plan for ECCCH's co-creation, knowledge sharing, and competitiveness across

diverse stakeholders including local authorities, private sector, and citizens. Complements the SRIA by operationalising stakeholder engagement mechanisms.

D18.2 – ECCCH Business Plan (M57) Led by E-RIHS. Strategic blueprint for ECCCH's long-term sustainable growth, encompassing governance, strategy, and funding. Translates SRIA sustainability principles into concrete economic models and financial strategies.

D18.3 – Sustainability Impact Assessment (M60) Led by ENCATC. Comprehensive analysis of ECCCH's activity-driven long-term changes, with recommendations to lower environmental footprint. Evaluates the implementation of SRIA environmental responsibility principles.

6.3 Sister Projects as Strategic Partners

The Sister Projects funded under the Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage action span diverse heritage domains—from archaeology and conservation to music, textiles, and archival sciences—and will be the primary agents bringing the ECCCH to their respective communities. Rather than viewing the current limited information about their activities as a constraint, this SRIA positions their forthcoming experiences as the primary mechanism for strategic refinement. As Sister Projects operationalise their activities, they will generate concrete use cases demonstrating the ECCCH's value across different domains, community-specific requirements for infrastructure development, and an evidence base that can inform both sustainability modelling and policy advocacy at national and European levels.

The primary vehicle for incorporating Sister Project insights into the SRIA is the ECCCH Integration Task Force (EITF), the cross-project coordination body established under WP3. The EITF operates as the single channel through which Sister Projects contribute bottom-up input to the strategic agenda, following a structured feedback cycle. At each meeting cycle, Sister Projects report on technical integration needs, community-specific requirements, barriers encountered, and emerging use cases. WP11 then synthesises this aggregated input against the SRIA's Priority Areas and Core Themes, identifying where the strategic agenda needs updating—new priorities, revised timelines, or validated assumptions.

In addition to the EITF cycle, several complementary mechanisms support continuous feedback integration: structured feedback sessions aligned with project milestones; a use case documentation protocol enabling consistent capture of successes and challenges across projects (feeding into both SRIA refinement and D18.1, Open Innovation Strategy); joint requirements workshops for collaborative identification of

community-specific needs; sustainability model co-development allowing Sister Projects to pilot the access models proposed in the Sustainability Framework; and cross-project knowledge exchange facilitating transfer of lessons learned between heritage domains. All mechanisms are coordinated through the EITF and aligned with WP10 (Governance) and WP15 (Community Building).

Early strategic signals from the first two waves of Sister Projects. At the time of writing (April 2026), 13 Sister Projects have responded to a structured Integration Questionnaire covering their integration needs, infrastructure requirements, and sustainability expectations. This is a partial sample: not all funded Sister Projects have responded, and the projects are at early stages of implementation. The observations below should therefore be read as preliminary signals, not as validated findings. They will be considered for integration into future SRIA updates as more complete data becomes available through the EITF cycle, provided such data yields insights that substantively improve or refine the SRIA’s strategic perspective.

Three patterns are worth noting for their strategic implications. First, every responding project assumes that the ECCCH will provide a set of foundational services—federated identity management, a queryable knowledge base, long-term storage, containerised deployment, and documented APIs—as pre-existing infrastructure into which they integrate. No project is developing these capabilities independently. This convergence confirms the centrality of Priority Area A (Infrastructure and Interoperability).

Second, the projects collectively surface a tension between semantic standardisation and domain-specific depth that no individual project can resolve. All reference CIDOC-CRM as a common denominator, but each extends it substantially for its domain—stratigraphy, colour science, textiles, interactive experiences, music heritage. The ECCCH’s capacity to accommodate this ontological diversity without fragmenting the knowledge base is a long-term research challenge that the SRIA positions within Priority Area A, Core Theme A.1 (Semantic Frameworks and Ontologies).

Third, sustainability emerges as a broader challenge than funding alone. Beyond covering storage and compute costs after project end, Sister Projects point to operational stewardship — maintaining code, retraining AI models, patching security, and governing ontology evolution — as the deeper question. The choice between centralised, federated, or hybrid operation has direct implications for the Sustainability Framework (Section 5, Priority Area C) and the ECCCH Business Plan (D18.2).

6.4 International Cooperation

Digital cultural heritage is inherently transnational: collections are dispersed across borders, archaeological sites span multiple jurisdictions, and the methodological challenges addressed by the ECCCH—semantic interoperability, long-term preservation, community-driven digitisation—are shared by institutions worldwide. Task 11.1.4 of the ECHOES work programme mandates the identification of frameworks for cooperation with non-EU initiatives, and a preparatory mapping exercise has been conducted to identify potential partners.

The mapping, covering the period March to June 2025, has identified a first shortlist of non-EU initiatives with thematic and operational relevance to the ECCCH, organised by geographic region. In Europe beyond the EU, these include the ALIPH Foundation (Switzerland), dedicated to heritage protection in conflict and crisis areas, and the UK’s Towards a National Collection programme. In the Middle East and North Africa, the Digital Library of the Middle East (DLME) offers a model for transnational digital collections. In Sub-Saharan Africa, the Open Restitution Africa project and the Sudan Memory programme represent emerging approaches to digitisation in contexts of conflict and restitution. In Asia-Pacific, Japan’s Consortium for International Cooperation in Cultural Heritage and Australia’s Trove platform represent mature national-scale digital heritage initiatives. In the Americas, the Coalition for Canadian Digital Heritage, the Library of Congress’s Computing Cultural Heritage in the Cloud programme, and the Ibero-American Digital Cultural Heritage network (ABINIA/SEGIB) offer complementary approaches.

At the global level, UNESCO’s Memory of the World programme and Information for All Programme (IFAP) provide normative frameworks for digital heritage preservation. The Council of Europe’s Faro Convention (2005), while European in origin, establishes principles of community participation and shared responsibility that inform the ECCCH’s governance approach and resonate with non-European partners.

This mapping is a preparatory step. Concrete cooperation frameworks—including bilateral agreements, joint pilot projects, and standard-alignment initiatives—will be developed progressively as the ECCCH’s own infrastructure matures and as partner initiatives reach comparable levels of readiness. The strategic principle is that the ECCCH should actively seek interoperability with non-European infrastructures where compatible standards exist (CIDOC-CRM, IIF, Linked Open Data, FAIR principles), avoiding the risk of developing a closed European system.

7. Conclusions

This Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda establishes the foundation for developing the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage as a sustainable, impactful infrastructure for Europe's digital cultural heritage ecosystem.

The key strategic orientations consolidated by this SRIA are:

- The ECCCH's Mission and Vision articulate a transformative approach to digital cultural heritage, where value emerges from connection and community contribution (Sections 1.1–1.2)
- The Value Proposition is built on scientific, technological, economic, and community/synergy dimensions, operationalised through six Guiding Principles (Sections 1.3 and 4)
- The three Priority Areas — Infrastructure and Interoperability, Communities and Capacity, Sustainability and Value Creation — translate principles into concrete research and innovation themes (Section 5)
- Sustainability is treated as a systemic responsibility: the sustainability of the digital infrastructure is inseparable from that of the physical cultural heritage it serves, since the long-term preservation of real heritage depends on resilient digital ecosystems, and digital infrastructures draw meaning from the heritage they document (Priority Area C)
- Implementation relies on funding, networking, governance, and community instruments, with Sister Projects and RIs providing the primary pathway for bottom-up validation and refinement (Section 6)
- The SRIA is a living document, evolving through structured feedback mechanisms across successive versions

The three Priority Areas—Infrastructure and Interoperability, Communities and Capacity, and Sustainability and Value Creation—provide the operational framework for achieving these orientations.

As Version 1.0, this document presents orientations validated by the ECHOES consortium and Steering Committee. The mechanisms established for Sister Project integration and coordination with subsequent WP11/WP18 deliverables ensure that strategic priorities will be refined as experience accumulates and community input is integrated.

Annexes

Annex A: Catalogue of European R&I Initiatives

This annex presents the mapping of the current European R&I landscape for digital cultural heritage, originally developed as T11.1.1. It identifies the key initiatives, infrastructures, and programmes that constitute the ecosystem within which the ECCCH operates.

A.1 Introduction – Scope of the document

Scope: evaluation – assessment to get to the SRI

The European landscape for research and innovation in digital cultural heritage is evolving rapidly. Europe has established itself as a **global leader in digital cultural heritage** and heritage science through numerous consortia, clusters, and initiatives that integrate advanced digital tools into heritage preservation, management and valorisation. Major European projects aim to enhance open science, data sharing, and innovative technologies such as 3D digitisation and AI. This document reviews the **most significant European initiatives**, providing a comprehensive view of Europe’s digital heritage landscape.

Recent European projects emphasise **interoperable infrastructures, data aggregation, and open science principles** to connect cultural heritage resources across diverse domains. This transformation is shaped by key initiatives and strategic priorities, such as the development of **data spaces** and **Research Infrastructures (RIs)** aimed at empowering cultural and scientific communities.

Macro-trends in the European landscape about the digital dimension of cultural heritage include:

1. **Data Interoperability and Aggregation:** Ensuring that cultural heritage data across RIs is standardised, easily discoverable, and reusable;
2. **Open Science Advocacy:** Increasing awareness and adoption of open science practices across cultural and academic institutions;
3. **Training and Capacity Building:** Developing skills among cultural professionals and researchers to manage and interpret digital data effectively;
4. **Collaborative Infrastructures:** Strengthening synergies between projects like EOSC and Europeana to build a cohesive, pan-European data space for cultural heritage.

Current European landscape for Research Infrastructures (RIs)

Europe’s Research Infrastructure (RI) landscape is complex, comprising **63 RIs** under the **ESFRI roadmap** (41 landmark RIs and 22 emerging projects). These infrastructures provide **data services, tools, and collaborative platforms** essential to advancing cultural heritage research and enhancing interdisciplinary connections (Chambers, 2024).

To streamline access to RI resources, projects like the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)** are integral. EOSC links RIs through a federated open science environment that facilitates data sharing, resource interoperability, and advanced data processing. Such integration is critical for cultural heritage data, which often involves diverse types of metadata, multilingual resources, and varied digital formats. Through projects such as OSCARS, EOSC aims to promote open science in Europe by connecting **thematic science clusters** that unify RIs and their communities.

The Role of Data Spaces in Cultural Heritage

In this context, the **Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage** is a key development aimed at consolidating Europe’s cultural assets into an accessible, sustainable digital ecosystem. This data space emphasises **3D digitisation**, multilingual access, and open data policies. By providing an environment where data can be securely stored, processed, and shared across Europe, the data space will strengthen the digital transformation of cultural institutions. Europeana’s role as a coordinating partner underscores its ongoing commitment to promoting open access to cultural heritage, while aligning with EU standards for digital preservation and accessibility.

Open Science and the SSH Open Marketplace

A crucial technological node in this context is the **SSH Open Marketplace**, developed under the **SSHOC (Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud)** project. This marketplace serves as a domain-specific portal for SSH researchers, aggregating data, tools, and workflows that comply with FAIR principles. It provides a model for integrating cultural heritage data with social sciences, emphasising curation, contextualisation, and user collaboration. The SSH Open Marketplace exemplifies how open science practices can be operationalised within specialised domains, fostering data interoperability and resource sharing among SSH disciplines.

Innovative digital tools and technologies for cultural heritage

Emerging technologies, such as **AI-based processing** of cultural heritage data, and tools for **data aggregation**, **natural language processing**, and **semantic analysis** can enhance the usability of complex datasets. Projects like **ECHOES** are focusing on integrating these tools to facilitate heritage preservation through **Digital Twins**, **3D modeling**, and **machine learning** for metadata enrichment. These innovations ensure that cultural heritage is preserved digitally, enhancing accessibility and promoting data reuse across research domains.

Funding for long-term sustainability and advancement

The **Research Infrastructure Working Programme** and the forthcoming **10th Framework Programme (FP10)**—set to succeed **Horizon Europe**—present significant opportunities for Research and Innovation (R&I) in digital cultural heritage. Both frameworks will continue advancing open science, data interoperability, and resource-sharing goals established in Horizon Europe.

The FP10 framework, anticipated to launch in the late 2020s, is expected to emphasise **sustainability**, **digital transformation**, and **technological sovereignty**. These themes resonate strongly with cultural heritage needs, particularly as they pertain to digitisation, preservation, and data accessibility. With FP10’s anticipated focus on **deep technologies** (such as AI, quantum computing, and advanced data analytics), cultural heritage projects could benefit from new resources for **3D modeling**, **AI-enhanced analysis**, and **digital twin technologies**. This approach aligns with the goals of projects like **ECHOES** and **SSHOC**, which leverage advanced digital infrastructures to manage and share complex cultural data.

The **Research Infrastructure Working Programme** under FP10 will likely prioritise interoperability across European RIs, with funding geared toward infrastructure that supports cross-disciplinary collaboration. For digital cultural heritage, this provides a critical avenue to enhance interoperability and adopt FAIR data practices. The Working Programme will offer opportunities to fund initiatives that promote **data standardisation**, **metadata enrichment**, and **collaborative platforms**, reinforcing efforts by Europeana and the SSH Open Marketplace to unify cultural heritage resources.

FP 10 will likely offer significant prospects for integrating cultural heritage data with broader research infrastructures, driving forward the open science agenda while fostering a sustainable digital ecosystem. R&I stakeholders in digital heritage should strategically align with these frameworks to maximise funding potential, particularly by

focusing on projects that promote long-term accessibility, innovative digital tools, and public engagement with cultural heritage.

A.1.1 ECHOES - European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science. Focus on the project

The ECHOES project (European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage) officially began on June 1, 2024, and will continue until May 31, 2029. Funded under the Horizon Europe program, ECHOES has been awarded a budget of €25 million to establish the ECCCH (European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage) a collaborative cloud infrastructure for cultural heritage professionals and researchers across Europe.

The ECHOES project is strategically positioned within Europe's digital cultural heritage landscape as a major initiative aimed at developing a Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage. Supported by Horizon Europe, ECHOES builds on the goals of other large-scale digital heritage projects like Europeana, EOSC, and SSHOC by creating an integrated, FAIR-compliant infrastructure that allows heritage professionals to collaboratively store, access, and analyse digital cultural assets. ECHOES aligns with the European Commission's priorities of digital transformation and open science by embedding advanced tools, such as AI and 3D modeling, into its platform to enhance data usability and enrich the accessibility of cultural heritage.

ECHOES stands out for its holistic approach to the interoperability and sustainability of cultural heritage data, functioning as both a repository and a knowledge-sharing space. By connecting with the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage and leveraging tools from EOSC's federated cloud infrastructure, ECHOES extends the reach of cultural heritage data across disciplines, promoting cross-sectoral research and public engagement. Positioned as a central player in Europe's digital heritage ecosystem, ECHOES is set to drive forward the open-access movement and foster collaboration among diverse cultural and scientific communities in Europe.

Consortium Members

ECHOES is led by the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) in France, with support from major partners including CNR (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche) in Italy and the Fondation des Sciences du Patrimoine (FSP). The consortium is extensive, consisting of 51 European partners from 15 EU member states, including academic institutions, cultural organisations, museums, libraries, archives, and private sector companies. Notable participants include the Europeana Foundation, Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft, Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage, The Cyprus Institute, and University of Helsinki, among others. This wide-ranging consortium represents a broad spectrum of

expertise across digital heritage, conservation, and technology, positioning ECHOES as a central hub for Europe's cultural heritage initiatives.

Objectives

The ECHOES project aims to create a Digital Commons for cultural heritage, an innovative digital environment that enables heritage professionals to collectively access, analyse, and enrich digital representations of cultural objects. The project is designed to support both tangible and intangible cultural heritage, encouraging a holistic approach to preservation that integrates open science principles. Key objectives include:

- **Building the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH)**, a central platform to consolidate EU and national projects on cultural heritage, which will enable sustainable data management and knowledge co-creation.
- **Promoting interoperability and data-sharing practices that align with FAIR principles** to ensure that cultural heritage data is accessible, reusable, and enriches the collective understanding of Europe’s cultural assets.
- **Developing advanced tools for digital transformation**, including **AI applications** and **3D modeling** tools, allowing users to create and interact with Digital Twins of heritage artifacts.
- **Establishing a transparent governance model** to manage the platform sustainably and inclusively, supporting collaborations across the cultural heritage and research communities.
- **Encouraging broad participation and knowledge sharing** through training programs, capacity building, and extensive community outreach, thus fostering a cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral approach to digital heritage.

ECHOES is set to be a transformative project that brings together a diverse set of actors within the cultural heritage field, integrating with other European initiatives like **EOSC** and the **Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage** to maximise accessibility, interoperability, and the digital impact on European heritage.

A.2 The European Landscape of long-term initiatives

A.2.1 EOSC (European Open Science Cloud)

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative was launched in 2016 as part of the European Commission's Open Science strategy, aiming to create an open, federated digital environment where researchers across disciplines can store, manage, analyse, and share data. EOSC represents a foundational shift in how data and digital resources are used within the European Research Area (ERA). While it was initially set to reach

maturity by 2027, EOSC is designed to be a sustainable, long-term infrastructure supporting the ongoing digital transformation of research and data-driven sectors across Europe.

Consortium and Governance

EOSC is supported by a diverse group of stakeholders, including major research infrastructures, public and private sector organisations, and European institutions. Key governing bodies include the EOSC Association, a central coordinating entity, which works closely with EOSC-A and various working groups to implement policies, set priorities, and maintain alignment with European open science standards. The association's membership includes prominent research and educational institutions, as well as domain-specific infrastructures like CESSDA for social sciences and E-RIHS for heritage science. EOSC also collaborates with large consortia such as ECHOES and Europeana, which leverage EOSC's digital infrastructure for sharing and preserving cultural heritage data.

Objectives

EOSC’s primary goal is to establish a **federated cloud environment** that promotes **FAIR principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), enabling open access to scientific data and resources across disciplines. Key objectives include:

- **Building a scalable, federated infrastructure** to support data sharing and cross-disciplinary collaboration, ensuring that European researchers can access and share data securely and efficiently.
- **Supporting data interoperability** by establishing standards, policies, and protocols that allow different data systems to communicate seamlessly. This is crucial for projects like **DIGILAB** and **SSHOC**, which depend on interoperable frameworks to manage and share cultural heritage data effectively.
- **Providing tools for data management and analysis**, including cloud computing, AI, and machine learning tools, enabling researchers to harness the full potential of big data.
- **Promoting open science practices** across Europe, with a particular focus on social sciences, humanities, and cultural heritage, which are traditionally data-siloed fields. EOSC’s support for open science enables projects such as **OSCARS** and **GRAPHIA** to access, analyse, and reuse data in innovative ways.

Impact and Sustainability

EOSC aims to be a long-term infrastructure that grows beyond its initial funding to become self-sustaining through partnerships and collaborative governance. By

integrating with domain-specific initiatives and working closely with European data spaces, EOSC is positioned to drive digital transformation in research and cultural sectors. Its impact is expected to support researchers, heritage professionals, and public institutions in the ongoing mission of data preservation, knowledge co-creation, and open-access innovation.

Possible Interactions, Synergies, and Opportunities Between EOSC and ECHOES

EOSC provides an ideal environment for ECHOES to leverage its federated, interoperable cloud infrastructure for the storage, sharing, and reuse of digital cultural heritage data. With EOSC's commitment to FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), ECHOES can ensure that the cultural heritage data it aggregates and digitises is readily accessible to researchers, heritage professionals, and the public across Europe. This integration also allows ECHOES to connect its Digital Commons-which enables collaborative access to heritage data-with the broader research community on EOSC, promoting interdisciplinary use and innovation. Opportunities arise in metadata standardisation and AI-driven analysis of cultural heritage data, as EOSC's infrastructure includes tools and protocols that enhance the value and usability of ECHOES' digital resources for European research communities.

EOSC is primarily funded through the European Commission's Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 frameworks, aiming to establish a sustainable, federated open science platform across Europe. The strategy behind EOSC's funding model is to create a public-private partnership that will ensure long-term sustainability beyond initial project funding. EOSC's funding strategy includes fostering collaborations with national and institutional stakeholders, integrating services from a variety of research infrastructures, and establishing co-financing arrangements for future infrastructure maintenance and development. EOSC encourages FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, with significant investments directed toward interoperability and data-sharing standards that can be widely adopted across research domains

A.2.2 E-RIHS (European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science)

The E-RIHS Implementation Phase (E-RIHS IP) began on October 1, 2022, and will conclude on December 31, 2024. E-RIHS is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe framework and is advancing toward establishing itself as a permanent European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) focused on heritage science.

E-RIHS and ECHOES have strong potential for collaboration, particularly through shared objectives around data interoperability and open science practices. By integrating ECHOES' collaborative cloud capabilities, E-RIHS can enhance its DIGILAB platform, providing even broader digital access and tools for the cultural heritage community. ECHOES' focus on advanced digital technologies, such as 3D modeling and AI, complements E-RIHS's aim to offer high-level diagnostics and data services. Both initiatives, when linked, can create a robust digital infrastructure that not only preserves heritage data but also makes it widely accessible and reusable, supporting Europe's commitment to open science in cultural heritage research.

Major Components, Partners, and Networks

E-RIHS is structured around a network of national nodes and prominent research infrastructures, such as ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, MOLAB, and DIGILAB. These facilities offer access to cutting-edge scientific tools for on-site analysis, mobile labs for non-invasive diagnostic techniques, fixed-location labs, and virtual repositories for heritage data. The infrastructure's coordination is led by Italy's Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR), with participation from 15 other European countries and support from global heritage institutions. E-RIHS collaborates closely with similar European Research Infrastructures to integrate advanced tools, knowledge, and data resources, forming a cohesive pan-European network for heritage science.

Objectives and Impact

E-RIHS aims to transform heritage science through an interdisciplinary approach that integrates technology, data, and expertise to support heritage conservation, documentation, and research. Its objectives include developing standardised, accessible heritage science resources, providing training through its HS Academy, and ensuring that all data and resources adhere to FAIR principles. E-RIHS is designed to support both small-scale studies and long-term projects, offering a comprehensive framework for research that enriches public understanding and sustainable preservation of cultural heritage across Europe.

The upcoming European DIGILAB within the E-RIHS framework represents a critical advancement for digital heritage science, offering a virtual research environment (VRE) that provides heritage researchers and institutions across Europe with access to cutting-edge digital tools and services. DIGILAB will enable the integration and analysis of diverse datasets-spanning 3D scans, imaging, and analytical results-thus supporting comprehensive heritage documentation and preservation. As a core component of E-RIHS, DIGILAB facilitates the sharing and standardisation of heritage science

methodologies and data, promoting interoperability and adherence to FAIR principles. This infrastructure will empower researchers to conduct virtual diagnostics, simulate conservation techniques, and collaborate on complex heritage research projects, ensuring that digital resources are both accessible and sustainable. DIGILAB aligns closely with E-RIHS's goal of establishing a pan-European infrastructure for heritage science, enhancing research quality and supporting the preservation of Europe's cultural heritage through advanced, digitally enabled methodologies.

Funding Policies and Strategies

Funded under Horizon Europe, E-RIHS is designed with a sustainable funding model that focuses on collaboration across European national nodes. E-RIHS also emphasises a harmonised membership fee structure, enabling broad participation and resource sharing. The project's approach includes building a robust business and risk management strategy that ensures sustainability beyond the Horizon Europe funding cycle, with the ERIC status supporting long-term funding and operational continuity.

A.2.3 ARIADNE RI

The ARIADNE Research Infrastructure AISBL (ARIADNE RI) is a digital research infrastructure for archaeology and heritage. It was founded on 28 November 2022. It is not-for-profit association, established according to Belgian law, but operating at an international level. Its primary aim is to continue the work of ARIADNEplus (2018-22) and the previous ARIADNE Integrating Activity (2012-16). By the end of 2022 these projects had established a Linked Open Data triple store, also searchable via an Open Access data catalogue (the ARIADNE portal). This has continued to grow and now provides access to over 4m rich data resources. These encompass the archaeology and heritage of 4 continents and over 40 countries and range from the archaeology of the earliest hominids to the present day.

Major Components, Partners, and Networks

As of 31 December 2024, the membership of the ARIADNE RI comprises 34 organisations. The majority are based within Europe, with one from Asia. Institutional members are a mix of universities, research institutes, data repositories and state heritage organisations and national museums. The ARIADNE technical infrastructure is maintained by a partnership of CNR (Italy), SND (Sweden), ADS (UK), PIN (Italy), and FORTH (Greece).

Objectives and Impact

The purpose of the ARIADNE RI is to:

- a. Promote, support and develop the use of digital techniques applied to the arts, humanities, cultural heritage and in particular to archaeology;
- b. Contribute to the development of software tools to operate on digital data in these sectors;
- c. Promote and encourage the creation of open archives with the data produced in these fields by research and management;
- d. Maintain and develop management tools allowing the integration of digital data archives in these sectors;
- e. Continue to manage the integration of the archaeological data archives developed in the ARIADNE and ARIADNEplus projects, expanding and updating the digital catalogue already available online and the associated digital infrastructure;
- f. Support this program with the necessary communication tools.

Based upon its broad membership it is able to represent the largest international grouping of archaeological data repositories, national heritage bodies, museums, scientific research organisations and universities. It also brings together archaeologists and information scientists in a collaboration that enables them to apply for international research funding as a single legal entity.

Funding Policies and Strategies

Members of the ARIADNE RI pay a nominal annual membership fee which maintains central office costs, but the core business model rests on payments for data publication in the portal. It was recognised during the ARIADNE and ARIADNEPlus projects, and in the SEADDA COST action that many countries lacked capacity to make their heritage data available online. Rather than organisations having to develop their own online interfaces there was demands for a chargeable data publication service. This is run on a not-for-profit basis to cover the staffing costs of the aggregation team, and the running costs of the technical infrastructure. In recent years, direct participation in EU-funded projects has provided a major income supplement and allowed the ARIADNE RI to recruit additional staff.

Possible Interactions, Synergies, and Opportunities Between ARIADNE RI and ECHOES

The ECCCH provides an opportunity for ARIADNE to extend its reach and impact beyond archaeology. This partnership will foster resource sharing, support the development of new means of data access, and enhance the visibility and accessibility of Europe’s archaeological heritage.

ECHOES and ARIADNE are both committed to fostering open science and data interoperability. By integrating with the ECCCH, ARIADNE can provide access to large tangible cultural heritage collections from a large number of data providers, and support professionals and researchers in processing, enriching, and analysing archaeological datasets, encompassing a broad range of data types.

The ARIADNE community provides access to key stakeholders in the heritage sector.

A.2.4 CLARIN

CLARIN stands for Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure and ERIC stands for European Research Infrastructure Consortium.

CLARIN is a digital infrastructure which provides easy and sustainable access to a broad range of language data and tools to support research in the humanities and social sciences, and beyond. CLARIN provides access to multimodal digital language data (text, audio, video) and advanced tools with which to explore, analyse or combine these datasets.

CLARIN was founded in 2012 and is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), an international legal entity established by the European Commission in 2009. CLARIN is one of the research infrastructures that was selected for the European Research Infrastructures Roadmap by ESFRI, the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures. In 2016, CLARIN received the status of a Landmark on the ESFRI roadmap.

CLARIN is a distributed digital infrastructure, with participating centres all over Europe and further afield, which include universities, research centres, libraries and public archives. Tools and data from different centres are interoperable so that data collections can be combined and tools from different sources can be chained to perform operations at different levels of complexity, regardless of their location.

Major Services, Partners, and Networks

CLARIN is based on a distributed network of organisations (or centres) that host language resources and related services. These centres each have their own expertise. Within a single country, they are often grouped into a national consortium.

Each consortium appoints one centre as a representative in CLARIN’s technical body, the Technical Centre Committee (TCC). This is where most of the technical work happens: Writing specifications, planning software development and organising the quality control for each of the centre candidates.

The independent Technical Centres Assessment Committee (TCAC) analyses each of the candidate centres and provides feedback with regards to compliancy to the technical and organisational requirements.

CLARIN's Technical Pillars are the following:

- Federated Identity: Letting users log in to protected data and services with their own institutional login and password
- Persistent Identifiers: Enabling sustainable citations of electronic resources
- Repositories: Digital archives where language resources can be stored, accessed and shared
- Component Metadata and concept definitions: To ensure semantic interoperability when describing language resources
- Content Search: Offering a search engine for a wide range of language resources
- Web service chaining: Giving users the possibility to freely combine language processing services.

Funding Policies and Strategies

CLARIN ERIC is funded through a combination of national contributions from its member countries and project-based funding under the European Union's research frameworks, such as Horizon Europe. This mixed funding model ensures both sustainability and adaptability, allowing CLARIN to respond to emerging research needs and technological advancements.

As an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium), CLARIN benefits from a stable governance and financial structure that enables long-term planning and resource allocation. In addition, it actively participates in collaborative projects, securing funding to expand its services and infrastructure.

CLARIN and ECCCH

ECCCH's collaborative cloud infrastructure represents an opportunity for CLARIN to amplify its reach and impact within the cultural heritage domain. This partnership will foster resource sharing, support the development of innovative digital tools, and enhance the visibility and accessibility of Europe's linguistic and cultural assets on a global scale.

ECHOES and CLARIN share a commitment to fostering open science and data interoperability. By integrating with the ECCCH, CLARIN can provide access to large

textual and linguistic cultural heritage collections, and support professionals and researchers in processing, enriching, and analysing multilingual heritage datasets.

A.2.5 DARIAH

DARIAH-EU (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) was first conceptualised in 2005 and officially established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) on 15 August 2014, with France as the host country. DARIAH is a distributed, pan-European research infrastructure whose mission is to empower research communities with digital methods to create, connect and share knowledge about culture and society. It develops, maintains and operates an infrastructure in support of ICT-based research practices, sustaining researchers in using them to build, analyse and interpret digital resources. DARIAH is one of the Landmarks on the Roadmap of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), reflecting its central role in the digital transformation of arts and humanities research across Europe.

Major Services, Partners, and Networks

DARIAH is structured around a network of national nodes spread across its member countries. As of 2024, DARIAH counts 23 member countries and a growing number of Cooperating Partner institutions in non-member countries, including partners outside Europe such as Princeton University in the United States. The founding members include Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Cyprus, Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Malta, the Netherlands, Serbia and Slovenia. Within each member country, a national consortium coordinates local digital humanities activities and connects them to the European-level infrastructure.

DARIAH's activities are organised through four Virtual Competency Centres (VCCs) and numerous self-organised Working Groups that address specific research themes and methodological challenges. Key services include the DARIAH Tools and Services Catalogue, which provides access to a diverse portfolio of core and community services, and DARIAH-Campus, an open-access discovery and hosting platform for learning resources in the digital humanities. DARIAH also co-manages the SSH Open Marketplace — a discovery portal developed together with CLARIN and CESSDA — which aggregates tools, services and datasets for the social sciences and humanities community. Additional initiatives include the Heritage Data Reuse Charter, developed in collaboration with Europeana, and the OpenMethods platform for sharing digital humanities methodologies.

Objectives and Impact

DARIAH's primary objective is to enhance and support digitally-enabled research and teaching across the arts and humanities. By bringing together individual state-of-the-art digital arts and humanities activities and scaling their results to a European level, DARIAH enables the transition to Open Science and beyond to Open Innovation. Key objectives include:

Providing researchers with access to digital resources, tools and services that support the full research lifecycle, from data acquisition and analysis to publication and archiving.

Promoting the adoption of FAIR principles and open science practices within the arts and humanities, fields that have traditionally relied on less standardised data management approaches.

Building digital skills and capacity through training programmes, workshops, summer schools and the DARIAH-Campus platform, ensuring that researchers can effectively leverage digital methods in their work.

Fostering cross-disciplinary and transnational collaboration by enabling communities to self-organise around emergent research themes through Working Groups, Hubs and other collaborative structures.

DARIAH's impact is seen in its capacity to connect fragmented national digital humanities communities into a cohesive European network, enabling knowledge exchange, methodological standardisation and the development of shared digital resources that serve researchers across disciplines and borders.

Funding Policies and Strategies

As an ERIC, DARIAH is primarily funded through annual membership fees paid by its member countries, calculated on the basis of each country's GDP. This membership-based model ensures stable governance and long-term financial sustainability, allowing DARIAH to plan strategically and allocate resources according to its multi-year strategic plans. In addition to membership contributions, DARIAH supplements its funding through active participation in EU-funded collaborative projects under frameworks such as Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe. Notable projects include DESIR (DARIAH-ERIC Sustainability Refined), which strengthened DARIAH's technical infrastructure and business model, and SSHOC (Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud), in which DARIAH played a central role. More recently, DARIAH is a key partner in ATRIUM (Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities) and OSCARS, both funded under Horizon Europe. DARIAH also operates an internal Working Groups Funding

Scheme, providing small-scale grants to support community-driven activities, innovation and the development of tools and training resources.

Possible Interactions, Synergies, and Opportunities Between DARIAH and ECHOES

DARIAH and ECHOES share a strong commitment to open science, data interoperability and the digital transformation of cultural heritage research. DARIAH's extensive expertise in digital humanities methodologies, metadata standards and community building can directly support ECHOES' mission to establish a European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH). By integrating with the ECCCH, DARIAH can contribute its rich portfolio of tools and services — including text analysis, data visualisation and annotation tools — as well as training resources via DARIAH-Campus, empowering cultural heritage professionals to adopt digital research methods.

The Heritage Data Reuse Charter, co-developed by DARIAH and Europeana, provides a shared framework for improving the conditions of access to and reuse of cultural heritage data, directly aligned with ECHOES' objectives of creating a Digital Commons. DARIAH's experience in managing the SSH Open Marketplace also offers a proven model for aggregating and contextualising digital tools and services that ECHOES can draw upon. Furthermore, DARIAH's Working Group structure and its capacity to mobilise distributed humanities research communities across Europe represent a valuable network for user engagement, co-design and participatory governance within the ECCCH. This partnership has the potential to amplify the impact of both infrastructures, bridging the gap between cultural heritage institutions and the broader arts and humanities research community.

A.2.6 OPERAS

OPERAS (Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities) is a distributed European research infrastructure dedicated to advancing open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH). First conceptualised in 2012 and formally shaped through a design phase from 2015 to 2018, OPERAS was selected for the ESFRI Roadmap in 2021 in recognition of its scientific excellence and strategic importance for the European Research Area. The OPERAS AISBL (a Belgian not-for-profit association) was incorporated in Brussels in 2020, providing the legal entity for the infrastructure during its preparatory phase. OPERAS is currently on the path toward establishment as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), targeted for 2027. Its mission is to coordinate and federate resources across

Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of SSH researchers, making Open Science a reality for these disciplines.

Major Services, Partners, and Networks

OPERAS is built as a federation of scholarly communication service providers, publishers, libraries, research institutions and individual researchers. Its governance is structured through a General Assembly and an Executive Assembly. The infrastructure actively collaborates with other SSH research infrastructures — notably DARIAH (which is a supporting member of OPERAS AISBL), CLARIN and CESSDA — as well as with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Association, of which OPERAS is a member.

OPERAS offers a growing catalogue of services organised around seven thematic categories: Discovery, Analytics, Quality Assurance, Research for Society, Training, and Operational and Collaborative services. Key operational services include GoTriple, a multilingual discovery platform that enables researchers to find and reuse open SSH scholarly resources across languages and repositories; PRISM Peer Review, provided through the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB), which enhances transparency of peer-review practices for open-access monographs; the Metrics Service, which collects usage and impact metrics for open-access books from multiple sources; VERA, a platform supporting citizen science and collaborative research projects; and Hypotheses, a research blogging platform. The Publishing Service Portal (Pathfinder) is under development to connect editors and editorial managers with appropriate publishing services.

Objectives and Impact

OPERAS' primary objective is to provide the SSH research community with the infrastructure it needs to find, access, create, edit, disseminate and validate scholarly outputs across Europe efficiently and without barriers. The European landscape of scholarly communication in SSH is characterised by fragmentation, small-scale service providers, historical underfunding and a diversity of languages, publication formats and cultural practices that are not adequately addressed by existing discipline-neutral e-infrastructures. OPERAS addresses this gap by pooling and federating existing resources at European scale, supporting the entire scholarly communication cycle. Key objectives include:

Enabling discovery and reuse of open scholarly resources in multiple languages, promoting multilingualism and bibliodiversity as core values of SSH research communication.

Improving quality assurance and trust in open-access publishing through standardised peer-review transparency and certification mechanisms.

Supporting the transition to Diamond Open Access — a model where neither authors nor readers pay fees — by building capacity among institutional publishers and service providers across Europe.

Fostering engagement between research and society through citizen science platforms and tools for public outreach, ensuring that SSH knowledge benefits the wider public.

OPERAS has a transformative impact by reducing disparities in access to scholarly information, fostering inclusivity and equity in academia and contributing to public trust in science by promoting transparency and openness in research communication.

Funding Policies and Strategies

OPERAS is currently in its implementation phase (2023–2027), funded primarily through EU-supported projects under Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe. The OPERAS-PLUS project (2022–2025), funded under Horizon Europe INFRADEV, supports the infrastructure's preparatory phase toward ERIC status, strengthening governance, developing the services portfolio and expanding the network of national nodes. Earlier projects such as OPERAS-D (design study), OPERAS-P (preparation), HIRMEOS (innovative services for open-access books) and TRIPLE (the GoTriple discovery platform) laid the foundation for the current service portfolio. OPERAS is also a partner in cross-infrastructure projects including SSHOC, DIAMAS (developing institutional open-access publishing models), CRAFT-OA (strengthening Diamond Open Access), ATRIUM and the Palomera project focused on open-access monographs. The PRIME project (Progressing the Research Infrastructure towards Maturity and ERIC Status) marks a further step toward consolidation. Upon establishment as an ERIC, OPERAS is expected to transition to a membership-fee-based funding model complemented by continuing participation in EU-funded collaborative projects.

Possible Interactions, Synergies, and Opportunities Between OPERAS and ECHOES

OPERAS and ECHOES share a fundamental commitment to open science, FAIR data principles and the democratisation of access to knowledge. OPERAS' expertise in open scholarly communication — particularly in supporting multilingual, diverse publication formats prevalent in cultural heritage scholarship — can directly strengthen the ECCCH's mission. The GoTriple discovery platform could be extended or federated with ECCCH services to enhance discoverability of research outputs related to cultural heritage, while

the PRISM certification service could support quality assurance for heritage-related open-access publications.

OPERAS' experience in fostering citizen science through the VERA platform aligns with ECHOES' goals of promoting participatory engagement between cultural heritage institutions and society. Furthermore, OPERAS' work on Diamond Open Access models and its advocacy for bibliodiversity and multilingualism are particularly relevant for cultural heritage research, which is inherently multilingual and relies on diverse publication formats including monographs, critical editions and digital collections. By collaborating, OPERAS and the ECCCH can ensure that scholarly communication infrastructure for cultural heritage research is inclusive, transparent and sustainable, amplifying the societal impact of both infrastructures.

A.2.7 Europeana and the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage

Europeana, founded in 2008, is the European Union's flagship digital library for cultural heritage. It offers a centralised online repository that hosts millions of digitised cultural assets from over 3,700 European museums, archives, and galleries. Through Europeana, users can access images, texts, audiovisual materials, and 3D artifacts from across Europe, all aimed at making European cultural heritage accessible to a broad audience and preserving it for future generations.

Objectives

Europeana's mission is to support digital transformation and interoperability within the cultural heritage sector, fostering an environment where data is readily accessible, reusable, and standardized. Under its 2020-2025 strategic framework, Europeana focuses on promoting high-quality metadata standards, enhancing interoperability through initiatives like the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF), and integrating 3D and AI technologies to enrich cultural content. Through these efforts, Europeana empowers cultural heritage institutions across Europe, helping them to contribute their collections to a shared digital space.

The Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage

Europeana now plays a central role in the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage, a recent initiative under the EU's Digital Europe Programme. This data space, launched in 2022, aims to accelerate the digital transformation of the European cultural sector by providing a collaborative, interoperable platform where cultural heritage data can be aggregated, enriched, and shared across Europe. The Europeana Foundation

coordinates this project in collaboration with a consortium of 19 partners from nine EU countries, and the initiative is overseen by the Commission Expert Group on the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage (CEDCHE).

The project is organised around four primary work areas:

1. **Infrastructure Development:** Establishing a robust infrastructure that ensures high-quality service and interoperability with other European data spaces.
2. **Data Integration:** Increasing the volume and quality of accessible cultural heritage data, with a particular emphasis on **3D digitisation**.
3. **Capacity Building:** Enhancing the digital skills of cultural heritage professionals and encouraging data reuse across the sector.
4. **Public Engagement:** Expanding pan-European digital access and creating interactive, multilingual content that engages the public and encourages data reuse in creative and educational contexts.

As Europe's foundational platform for digital cultural heritage, Europeana-now extended by the Common European Data Space-continues to set standards for digital preservation, data accessibility, and the public's engagement with cultural heritage. By fostering cross-border collaborations and supporting projects like ECHOES and 4CH, Europeana plays a crucial role in creating a shared digital ecosystem that ensures European cultural heritage is accessible, preserved, and actively used by diverse communities across Europe.

Possible Interactions, Synergies, and Opportunities Between Europeana and ECHOES

As Europe's largest digital cultural heritage platform, Europeana complements ECHOES by offering well-established aggregation and access frameworks for cultural heritage data. Europeana's recent expansion into the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage presents significant synergy with ECHOES by providing a model for aggregating, enriching, and distributing high-quality 3D and multimedia heritage content. Both initiatives share goals of public engagement and data reuse, and ECHOES can utilise Europeana's standards for metadata quality and digital preservation to ensure that its cultural heritage data aligns with Europe's digital heritage standards. Moreover, Europeana's broad user base and public engagement initiatives offer ECHOES valuable pathways for outreach, maximising visibility, and enhancing public interaction with digital heritage data

Europeana, funded initially under the Digital Europe Programme, is backed by the European Commission with a focus on enhancing digital cultural heritage access and

preservation. Funding for Europeana aims to establish it as a long-term, self-sustaining infrastructure by providing technical resources, tools, and training to European cultural institutions. The recently launched Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage expands on this foundation, incorporating a broader funding strategy to integrate 3D digitisation and data-sharing standards. This data space is part of the European Union's broader Digital Strategy, which seeks to digitise and consolidate Europe's cultural assets through partnerships with public and private institutions, ensuring cultural data's security, accessibility, and adaptability to new technological advances.

A.2.8 SSHOC (Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud)

The SSHOC project (Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud) ran from January 2019 to April 2022. As part of the Horizon 2020 program, SSHOC aimed to integrate the social sciences and humanities (SSH) research domain into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) by creating a cloud-based, FAIR-compliant environment for SSH data and resources.

Major Components, Partners, and Networks

SSHOC involved a network of 53 partners representing prominent research infrastructures and institutions, including CESSDA (Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives), CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure), DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities), and LIBER (Association of European Research Libraries). This consortium was instrumental in consolidating SSH research data, tools, and services into a unified cloud infrastructure, facilitating access and interoperability across Europe. SSHOC's major component, the SSH Open Marketplace, serves as a domain-specific portal that aggregates SSH data, tools, and services tailored for researchers, creating an accessible ecosystem for SSH resources.

Objectives and Impact

SSHOC's primary objective was to dismantle data silos within the SSH domain, establishing a cloud-based network that enables seamless access to and sharing of SSH data. Through the SSH Open Marketplace, the project provided SSH researchers with a centralised hub for accessing digital tools, datasets, and workflows, all adhering to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). SSHOC has had a significant impact on data sharing and interoperability within the SSH community, promoting cross-disciplinary research and increasing the usability of SSH data within the EOSC ecosystem.

Funding Policies and Strategies

SSHOC was funded by the Horizon 2020 program under the European Union's Research and Innovation (R&I) framework, with an emphasis on preparing the SSH domain for EOSC integration. Funding supported the development of infrastructure that meets the specific requirements of SSH, with a focus on ensuring sustainability beyond the project's end date. Post-project, the SSH Open Marketplace and other resources developed by SSHOC are maintained by the SSH Open Cluster, which is led by main SSH infrastructures such as CLARIN, CESSDA, and DARIAH.

Possible Interactions, Synergies, and Opportunities with ECHOES

The SSHOC infrastructure and ECHOES share a common goal of enhancing data interoperability and open access within EOSC. Through the SSH Open Marketplace, SSHOC provides a tested model for ECHOES to develop its Digital Commons, showing how cultural heritage data, tools, and best practices can be aggregated for wide accessibility and reusability. Additionally, SSHOC's expertise in managing multilingual and metadata-rich data specific to SSH can help ECHOES improve its approaches to metadata standardisation, resource discovery, and user engagement in the cultural heritage domain. This collaboration could foster greater integration of cultural heritage data within the SSH community, promoting interdisciplinary research that leverages both SSH and cultural heritage resources within EOSC.

A.2.9 4CH (Competence Center for the Conservation of Cultural Heritage)

The 4CH project started on January 1, 2021, and ran for three years, concluding in December 2023. It is funded under Horizon 2020 and focuses on establishing a robust framework for the digital preservation and conservation of European cultural heritage.

Major Components, Partners, and Networks

Coordinated by Italy's Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN), 4CH brings together 19 partners across academia, industry, and cultural institutions from 11 European countries. This multidisciplinary consortium includes institutions such as the Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen (KNAW), The Cyprus Institute, and Leica Geosystems AG. The project collaborates with a network of national, regional, and local cultural institutions to support and guide the conservation of historical monuments and sites. The core components of 4CH include the development of ICT tools, digital skills training, and collaborative support systems, with a particular focus on 3D technologies for heritage management and preservation.

Objectives and Impact

4CH's primary objective is to create a European Competence Centre dedicated to cultural heritage preservation and conservation, emphasising a holistic and multidisciplinary approach. The project aims to provide tools and resources for cultural heritage institutions to effectively digitise, manage, and conserve monuments and heritage sites. Key impacts include the establishment of best practices for heritage conservation, enhanced digitisation efforts through advanced 3D visualisation, and the development of protocols for integrating cultural heritage data with digital monitoring technologies. By promoting standardised methods and collaborative approaches, 4CH supports cultural heritage professionals across Europe in safeguarding and enhancing access to historical sites.

Funding Policies and Strategies

As part of the Horizon 2020 funding framework, 4CH operates with a budget of approximately €3 million. This funding supports infrastructure development, training programs, and technology deployment to ensure the Centre's sustainability and long-term impact on cultural heritage. The project's funding strategy involves fostering partnerships with various stakeholders, including government agencies, SMEs, and creative industries, to extend the Centre's reach and encourage broader adoption of its tools and standards across Europe.

Possible Interactions, Synergies, and Opportunities with ECHOES

There are several synergistic opportunities between 4CH and ECHOES, particularly in the realms of digital documentation and data accessibility. 4CH's focus on developing ICT tools and best practices for 3D digitisation aligns with ECHOES' objectives of creating a Digital Commons for cultural heritage. By collaborating with ECHOES, 4CH can expand its reach and support the integration of its 3D models and conservation protocols within ECHOES' digital cloud infrastructure, enhancing accessibility and reusability across Europe. Additionally, ECHOES can benefit from 4CH's expertise in ICT and monitoring technologies, which could be leveraged to enhance metadata standards and interoperability in cultural heritage data. Together, these projects contribute to building a cohesive and sustainable ecosystem for digital cultural heritage in Europe.

A.3 Emerging Projects and Technologies

A.3.1 OSCARS (Open Science Cluster for Research and Society)

The OSCARS project commenced on January 1, 2024, and will run for four years, concluding in December 2027. It is funded under the Horizon Europe framework with a grant aimed at fostering the uptake of open science in Europe.

Major Components, Partners, and Networks

OSCARS is coordinated by CNRS (Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique), involving 15 leading European Research Infrastructures (RIs) across five thematic science clusters: Social Sciences and Humanities (SSHOC), Life Sciences (EOSC-Life), Environmental Sciences (ENVRI-FAIR), Photon and Neutron Science (PaNOSC), and Astronomy & Particle Physics (ESCAPE). Key partners from these clusters, including institutions like CLARIN, DARIAH, and CESSDA, contribute to OSCARS' vision and work plans, ensuring interdisciplinary collaboration and data sharing across domains.

Objectives and Impact

OSCARS seeks to integrate and consolidate the achievements of the five science clusters initiated under Horizon 2020, transforming their outputs into sustainable, FAIR-compliant data services and practices. By establishing Community-Based Competence Centres (CCCs) and offering Composable Open Data and Analysis Services (CODAS), OSCARS strengthens data interoperability and accessibility, making data and tools available to a broad range of scientific disciplines. Additionally, OSCARS will drive the uptake of FAIR-data-intensive research through a cascading grant mechanism with an €16 million fund to support open science projects across the European Research Area (ERA).

The impact of OSCARS will be seen in its ability to foster cross-disciplinary connections, allowing scientific communities to engage with EOSC, adopt open science practices, and utilise harmonised data models for research and societal benefits.

Possible Interactions, Synergies, and Opportunities with ECHOES

OSCARS' focus on consolidating and enhancing data interoperability aligns well with ECHOES' goals for cultural heritage data accessibility. By linking ECHOES' Digital Commons with OSCARS' FAIR data initiatives, both projects can promote the reuse of cultural heritage data within the SSH community and beyond. Furthermore, the OSCARS cascading grant model offers ECHOES an avenue for funding smaller, complementary

projects that enhance the digital documentation and analysis of cultural assets. This synergy could lead to integrated workflows and training modules, amplifying the reach and impact of ECHOES within the broader research infrastructure community.

Funded under the Horizon Europe program, OSCARS has a unique funding model focused on supporting cluster-based, interdisciplinary collaborations in open science. It includes a cascading grant mechanism, allocating approximately €16 million in smaller grants to enable open science projects across the European Research Area (ERA). This funding strategy supports the open science uptake in various research domains, particularly by funding projects that align with FAIR principles and interoperability standards. The OSCARS funding model also emphasises capacity-building and infrastructure-sharing across its five thematic clusters, enhancing the overall resilience and accessibility of European research infrastructures.

A.3.2 H2IOSC (Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud)

The H2IOSC project officially began on November 1, 2022, with a projected completion date of April 30, 2025. It is funded under Italy’s PNRR (National Recovery and Resilience Plan), with an investment of €41.7 million. This project is one of the key national efforts aimed at establishing a federated infrastructure for humanities and cultural heritage within Italy, aligning with broader European goals for open science and digital transformation.

Major Components, Partners, and Networks

Coordinated by the **Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)**, H2IOSC integrates four Italian nodes of major European research infrastructures:

1. **CLARIN-IT** (for language resources and technologies),
2. **DARIAH-IT** (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities),
3. **OPERAS-IT** (Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area), and
4. **E-RIHS.it** (European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science).

This powerful network leverages high-performance computing nodes and digital laboratories, offering a diverse array of services and resources for digital humanities and heritage science.

Objectives and Impact

H2IOSC aims to support open science practices in the humanities and cultural heritage fields, using the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as a model for cross-disciplinary data sharing and interoperability. Key objectives include:

- Creating a unified digital infrastructure that facilitates data access, analysis, and reuse across research institutions and cultural organisations in Italy.
- Enhancing digital literacy and research capabilities in heritage science through innovative tools and training.
- Fostering international collaboration, making Italian cultural heritage data and research outputs accessible and interoperable within the broader European research landscape.

The impact of H2IOSC is substantial, as it establishes a sustainable model for open science in the humanities, promoting cross-sector collaboration and digital accessibility of Italian cultural heritage on a global scale.

Possible Interactions, Synergies, and Opportunities with ECHOES

The H2IOSC and ECHOES projects share complementary goals of enhancing open access to cultural heritage data and ensuring interoperability across research infrastructures. By connecting H2IOSC's specialised infrastructure in Italy with ECHOES' Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage, both projects can foster broader European cooperation and data exchange. This synergy would enable Italian cultural heritage data to be integrated seamlessly into ECHOES' Digital Commons, expanding the accessibility of high-quality heritage data across Europe. Additionally, H2IOSC's training resources and high-performance computing capabilities could serve as valuable assets within ECHOES, strengthening both projects' impact on the preservation and study of European cultural heritage.

H2IOSC is funded by Italy's PNRR (National Recovery and Resilience Plan), with an investment of €41.7 million dedicated to building a federated digital infrastructure for humanities and heritage science in Italy. Its funding strategy aligns with the European Union's NextGenerationEU recovery framework, which supports digital transformation and innovation within national contexts. H2IOSC's financial model involves close collaboration with established European research infrastructures such as CLARIN, DARIAH, OPERAS, and E-RIHS, allowing shared resource funding and access to advanced digital tools. By integrating with these infrastructures, H2IOSC's funding also supports sustainable knowledge-sharing and digital skill-building initiatives.

A.3.3 RICHeS (Research Infrastructure for Conservation and Heritage Science)

The RICHeS programme was launched on September 1, 2024, with long term funding from UKRI. The RICHeS programme will unlock access to heritage science facilities by

creating a distributed infrastructure of heritage science collections and equipment, joined together by the Heritage Science Data Service.

Major Components, Partners, and Networks

RICHeS comprises: (a) a Headquarters at STFC Hartree; (b) the Heritage Science Data Service (HSDS), co-hosted with the Archaeology Data Service (ADS) at the University of York; and (c) a first phase of 30 funded projects across the UK, comprising 17 facilities and 13 collections. RICHeS will provide the UK hub for E-RIHS, and the HSDS forms the UK's DIGILAB.

Objectives and Impact

RICHeS is the UK's Research Infrastructure for Conservation and Heritage Science. It is a long term, £80 million commitment from the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) part of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) to support excellence and collaboration within heritage and conservation science.

It will maximise the research and innovation potential of the UK heritage science by delivering a step change in sector effectiveness, efficiency and excellence. Specifically, it will:

- catalyse the development of an informed, collaborative and innovative UK heritage science community;
- ensure that the heritage science sector has the capability and the capacity to meet user demand and deliver world-class scientific excellence;
- ensure that heritage science equipment, expertise, resources and research data are findable and accessible to users, available to external stakeholders, and capable of being leveraged by a range of partners.

Possible Interactions, Synergies, and Opportunities with ECHOES

The HSDS has an equivalent role to that of H2IOSC in Italy and can have a similar interaction with ECHOES. Alongside the ADS it aims to ensure interoperability across research infrastructures, and to enhance open access and data re-use. The ADS is a CoreTrustSeal accredited repository ensuring the digital preservation of heritage data into the long term. Over the last 25 years it has developed a unique charging model which ensures that data is free at the point of use, but sustainability is guaranteed via one-off charges to data creators levied at the point of deposit. By connecting HSDS with ARIADNE, E-RIHS and with ECHOES' Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage, it can support broader European cooperation and data exchange. This synergy would enable

UK cultural heritage data to be integrated seamlessly into ECHOES, expanding the accessibility of high-quality heritage data across Europe. Additionally, ADS and HSDS training materials and high-performance computing capabilities could serve as valuable assets within ECHOES, strengthening the preservation and study of European cultural heritage.

A.3.4 GRAPHIA (Knowledge Graphs and AI for SSH)

- Overview: GRAPHIA is an AI-focused project launched in 2023 to develop knowledge graphs for social sciences and humanities, running until 2026.
- Objectives: Utilises AI for metadata enrichment and data visualisation, connecting SSH research data to broader digital infrastructures.
- Participants: Academic and research institutions specialising in AI and SSH.
- Impact: GRAPHIA contributes to advancing AI in SSH and serves as a model for applying AI-driven tools to analyse and preserve cultural heritage data.

A.4 Conclusion and Future Outlook

Europe's digital heritage landscape is robust, driven by initiatives like ECHOES, DIGILAB, and H2IOSC. By fostering collaboration across disciplines and leveraging technologies such as AI and 3D digitisation, Europe is setting new standards for cultural preservation in the digital age. The support of major consortia and emerging projects will ensure that European heritage remains accessible and sustainable for generations to come.

The integration of digital services and resources across European Research Infrastructures demonstrates Europe's commitment to preserving and sharing its cultural heritage. By advancing open science, promoting data interoperability, and leveraging cutting-edge technologies, Europe is establishing a sustainable digital heritage landscape that serves both the cultural and scientific communities. Chambers' insights underscore the importance of collaborative strategies and innovation-driven frameworks that ensure cultural data remains accessible, secure, and impactful for generations to come.

References

Richards, J.D. and F. Niccolucci (eds.) (2019) *The ARIADNE Impact*. Archaeolingua <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4319058>>

Chambers, S. (2024). *Joining up digital services and resources for Research Infrastructures: perspectives from the Social Sciences and Humanities*, Keynote speech, Belgian Presidency Conference, "Research Infrastructures in a Changing Global, Environmental and Socio-economical Context" (4-5 June 2024), Royal Library of Belgium (KBR), Brussels.

CLARIN ERIC (2024). CLARIN – European Research Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technology. <<https://www.clarin.eu/>>

DARIAH-EU (2019). DARIAH Strategic Plan 2019–2026. DARIAH-ERIC. <https://www.dariah.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/Strategic-Plan_2019-2026.pdf>

DARIAH-EU (2024). DARIAH – Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities. <<https://www.dariah.eu/>>

E-RIHS (2024). European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science. <<https://www.e-rihs.eu/>>

EOSC Association (2024). European Open Science Cloud. <<https://eosc.eu/>>

ESFRI (2021). Strategy Report on Research Infrastructures: Roadmap 2021. European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures. <<https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/>>

Europeana Foundation (2024). Europeana – Europe's Digital Cultural Heritage Platform. <<https://www.europeana.eu/>>

European Commission (2022a). Report on a European collaborative cloud for cultural heritage. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. Publications Office of the European Union. <<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/90f1ee85-ca88-11ec-b6f4-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>>

European Commission (2022b). Recommendation on a common European data space for cultural heritage. COM/2021/7953 final.

European Commission (2024). Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023–2024: Research Infrastructures. European Commission.

Niccolucci, F. and Richards, J.D. (2019). ARIADNE and ARIADNEplus. In: Richards, J.D. and F. Niccolucci (eds.), *The ARIADNE Impact*. Archaeolingua. <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4319058>>

OPERAS (2023). OPERAS Strategic Plan 2023–2025. OPERAS AISBL. <<https://operas-eu.org/>>

OPERAS (2024). OPERAS – Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities. <<https://operas-eu.org/>>

OSCARS Consortium (2024). OSCARS – Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society. <<https://oscars-project.eu/>>

RICHeS Programme (2024). Research Infrastructure for Conservation and Heritage Science. UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). <<https://riches.ac.uk/>>

SSHOC Consortium (2022). Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud: Final Report. Horizon 2020 Grant Agreement No. 823782. <<https://sshopencloud.eu/>>

Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J. et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Scientific Data 3, 160018. <<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>>

Annex B: PESTEL Analysis Detailed Findings and Foresight Analysis Methodology and Results

This annex presents the detailed PESTEL analysis and foresight exercise conducted under T11.1.2. It provides the full analytical basis for the strategic context presented in the main body of this SRIA.

B.1. Introduction

B1.1 Context and rationale

The European cultural sector is experiencing a period of significant transformation, resulting in accelerated pace of digitalisation, environmental, geopolitical, and regulatory changes. Cultural heritage actors, researchers, and communities are confronted to the rapid development of data infrastructures, the rise of Artificial Intelligence and the growing imperative of sustainability and resilience.

At the European policy level, the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 outlines strategic objectives for enhancing Europe's digital capacities, including cloud and data infrastructures, skills, as well as secure digital environments. This policy initiative underlines the significance of digital sovereignty as well as the requirement for investing in European data spaces as a crucial component of Europe's future competitiveness and societal resilience.

The climatic risk is also becoming more and more urgent for cultural heritage as extreme weather conditions and environmental changes are jeopardising tangible as well as intangible heritage, necessitating a new approach to safeguarding, adapting to, and sharing knowledge about these impacts.

As a consequence, the European regulation environment is rapidly evolving to tackle these elements. The EU Artificial Intelligence Act was adopted in August 2024, launching a full governance regime for AI systems, with significant implications for Cultural Heritage data, services, and the use of AI tools in a collaborative environment.

B1.2 The ECCCH and the ECHOES project

In this context, the ECHOES project is working to implement the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH), a collaborative digital space that will ease access to digitised information about heritage pieces to the general public and allow professionals

and researchers in the field of cultural heritage to work together, share interoperable services, and create knowledge and digital resources on a large scale.

To reach its goals, the ECHOES consortium is working towards creating an ecosystem where technologies such as semantic enrichment, AI services, and digital twins can be used in an open, participatory, and sustainable framework in Europe.

B1.3 Purpose and scope of this foresight

This foresight analysis feeds into the strategic development of the ECCCH through the identification of key future trends, drivers, uncertainties, and opportunity areas that will influence the future of research and innovation over the coming decade.

This foresight analysis was created to help the long-term strategic focus of the ECCCH in the ECHOES project. The aim of this foresight analysis is not to forecast a specific future scenario, but to explore the most important drivers of change, trends, and uncertainties that could influence the future of cultural heritage research and innovation in the next ten years.

This method is in line with the definition of Strategic Foresight as a means to improve resilience and flexibility in situations where there is a high pace of technological, societal, and environmental change.

The purpose of this foresight analysis is to offer strategic direction to ECCCH partners and stakeholders with a view to designing an infrastructure that is robust, inclusive, future-proofed, and aligned to emerging European priorities.

B.2. Methodology

B2.1 Evidence base and data sources

The methodology combines three complementary streams of evidence:

B2.1.1 Project mandate and structural context

The foresight is rooted in the objectives, logic of governance, and sustainability goals of ECHOES as set out in the Grant Agreement. Specifically, ECHOES conceptualises the ECCCH as a European digital commons that is sustained by a long-term legal entity, which is economically, socially, and environmentally sustainable.

B2.1.2 ECHOES' PESTLE analysis

A structured PESTLE exercise was carried out within WP11 to obtain views from partners about the key external factors that will influence ECCCH's development. Six 'Thematic Notes Form' documents were produced. This exercise systematically captured partner perspectives on external drivers likely to influence ECCCH development across six dimensions:

- Political
- Economic
- Social
- Technological
- Legal
- Environmental

These 'Notes Form' documents provide the main internal evidence for the trend identification process and identify also:

- key trends and drivers;
- impact level and time horizon;
- critical uncertainties;
- risks and opportunities for ECCCH.

B2.1.3 Strategic papers

European policy and scientific papers relating to digitalisation, AI governance, sustainability, and climate change (as outlined in the Bibliography).

B2.2 Analytical process

This analytical process has been informed by an abductive logic inspired by best practices in foresight methodologies that have been widely adopted in the cultural heritage field. Informed by this methodological tradition, the ECCCH foresight process has involved the following steps:

B2.2.1 Collection of partner signals through the WP11 PESTLE exercise,

resulting in thematic-based meetings held online from May to June 2025 and a series of form to collect and categorise relevant priorities, ensuring all aspects of political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental dimensions are covered.

B2.2.2 Thematic consolidation of the PESTLE results, including all

overlapping drivers and issues across the different categories (for example, funding sustainability in the political and economic categories).

B2.2.3 Dimension-based synthesis. Keeping the PESTLE structure, the

analysis allows each dimension to be examined independently and also maintain awareness of cross-domain interactions.

B2.2.4 ECCCH relevance assessment. For each dimension, implications for

ECCCH were derived by linking external drivers to potential consequences for infrastructure design, governance, adoption, sustainability, and strategic positioning.

B2.2.5 Identification of strategic uncertainties, focusing on factors

with high potential impact but uncertain future trajectories (for example, funding continuity after 2027 or legal interoperability of IPR systems).

B2.3 Scope and limitations

This is an exploratory foresight. Like other foresight exercises, it does not aim for exhaustive coverage of all possible futures. The outcomes will depend on various external factors.

Additionally, it should be noted that the PESTLE evidence is based on the views of the partners who participated in the project at a particular point in the project lifecycle. This will have to be continuously updated as the ECCCH moves towards implementation and governance.

B.3 The Six PESTLE Dimensions

B.3.1 Political Dimension

Context and key drivers

The political conditions in which ECCCH is evolving are influenced by the increasing focus on issues such as digital sovereignty, infrastructure security, cross-border collaboration and the role of "shared Digital Assets." Concurrent to this are changes in the priorities of public funding, which are evolving in response to the geopolitical environment, economic pressure and competing policy agendas.

At the European level, Digital Infrastructures are increasingly framed as strategic assets that support economic resilience and technological independence. The European Union's Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 institutes a framework for coherently building

Europe's Digital Capacity through Digital Infrastructure (Cloud Services and Data Infrastructures), Digital Ecosystems (Secure Digital Ecosystems) and Digital Cooperation (Cross-Border Digital Cooperation) through EC-funded projects. These policies will enhance the expectations that sectoral infrastructures, such as ECCCH, will deliver to more extensive European strategic digital objectives.

At the same time, infrastructure protection priorities are being redefined due to geopolitical developments. Digital infrastructures are increasingly viewed across numerous sectors as potential targets for cyber threat and hybrid risk, entailing a growing attention to security and infrastructure protection in policies across multiple countries. The partners in the consortium discussed the possibility that cultural heritage digital infrastructures will increasingly be defined as part of critical infrastructure or strategic asset discourse.

The complexity of governance across multiple institutional levels is a major political concern. At the National level, cultural heritage policy is dispersed among multiple ministries and agencies including Culture, Research, and Digital Transformation.

ECCCH operates within a Multi-Level Governance. Partners identified coordination challenges and policy fragmentation as structural impediments that will influence how ECCCH is implemented and how it will be governed over time.

Finally, political priorities at both the EU and national levels are being reshaped by fiscal constraints and changing security priorities. Partner's apprehensions that Public Investment will increasingly favour defence, security and strategic industrial policy may diminish available resources for cultural heritage-related infrastructure.

Implications for ECCCH

The implications that are anticipated for the ECCCH as an institution to develop strategically under the Political dimension of Cloud are:

1. Aligning the ECCCH's strategic development with the European; strategic infrastructure narratives is necessary; and to gain long-term political support and funding sustainability it will increasingly become a jurisdictional integration tool to demonstrate the ECCCH's contributions to the European digital sovereignty and digital knowledge infrastructure.
2. Political expectations (i.e., Cybersecurity and Infrastructure; Resilience) will increasingly accompany technical choices regarding Continuity and Resilience associated with Vulnerability and Risk management as the ECCCH progresses towards developing Digital Heritage Infrastructures.

3. The ability to coordinate multiple levels of governance is going; to be a major operational challenge for the ECCCH. Indeed, it must continue to operate across diverse and often fragmented policy environments and governance institutions. This will require the ECCCH to establish governance structures capable of traversing multiple levels (e.g., EU, National, Institutional) of policy simultaneously.
4. The possibility of the ECCCH to provide evidence of its importance; to society as well as to provide evidence of its importance to broad European policy priorities (e.g., Digital Transformation, Digital Knowledge Sovereignty, and Societal Resilience) will be critical as public funds become increasingly competitive.

Strategic uncertainties

- Would there be an official designation as Strategic or Critical for cultural heritage digitised networks/Infrastructure(s)?

If so, ECCCH would likely receive increased levels of attention from, and protection by, political entities but possibly also increased regulations, security, or governance-obligations.

- How do long-term political priorities likely change with time in the various EU funding cycles?

Potentially significant shifts in the EU's and Member States' budget priorities may dramatically impact current and future support available for culturally-related digital infrastructure (i.e., collections; heritage sites; archives), especially in a possible context of Global geopolitical and fiscal hardship.

- To what extent will ECCCH be able to harmonise a uniform policy across its Member States that have different strategic priorities?

The differences or divergences in national policies of Digital; Cultural; Research will have an impact on the speed of ECCCH deployment (what is launched and when), the harmonisation of governance policies (how things are governed once launched), and the method/form used to adopt the ECCCH within member countries.

B.3.2 Economic Dimension

Context and key drivers

Three interacting pressures influence the economic environment that affects ECCCH:

- Long-term uncertainty in the availability of public funding for

investment in Europe.

- Increasing volatility and cost of digital services and infrastructure.
- Rising expectations for the ability to show how much value and impact you create as a condition of continued funding support.

Competition for publicly funded projects is increasing. The European Commission recently submitted its proposal for the next EU long-term budget (2028-2034). It has framed the budget around its strategic priority areas: sovereignty, competitiveness and resilience. While there are no specifics in the proposal regarding cultural heritage allocations, the proposal indicates that funding will be increasingly tied to strategic policy priorities, and competition across areas is expected to increase.

Macroeconomic conditions have an impact on the operational costs of the areas. Eurozone inflation remains an important consideration when developing budgets for wage costs, procurement, and service contracts. Eurostat's formal indicators show a consistent increase in the level of inflation over the last several years, which partners relate directly to pressures on Information and Communication Technologies costs.

The third factor in driving the need for ECCCH is the focus on evidence of performance and results. The European Commission's interim review of Horizon Europe highlights how key evaluation and impact measurements will play an important role in making programme decisions as well as planning for the future. This type of approach also affects how the current justification for supporting large scale infrastructures will be made in the future.

Finally, participants provided PESTLE updates related specifically to economic risks of suppliers that are non-European with downstream impacts on either inclusion or sustainability.

Implications for ECCCH

- Designing for economic sustainability must occur upfront within the infrastructure (permanently designed features) and not as an added feature later in the life of the infrastructure;

> ECCCH must provide a clear path from project funding to sustained > operations. This path will need to consider coverage of costs > associated with operations, governance for reinvesting in the > infrastructure and developing a realistic operational model over the > duration of the life of ECCCH.

- Cost structure will drive participation and fairness;

> If operational costs of the project and/or cost to access (i.e. fees, > technical requirements, staff time) will increase, ECCCH will > substantially reinforce existing inequalities inherent to those > institutions. Therefore, economic design shall provide access > opportunities for inclusion.

- The prevention of provider lock-in is a high priority in economic risk management;

> Supplier-customer interdependence has the potential for increased > long-term costs, reduced bargaining power, and reduced independence. > ECCCH will require purchasing and design decisions to reduce the risks > associated with structural dependency. The value proposition for ECCCH > will likely be a clearly stated \"value proposition\" tied to > measurable outcomes. This aligns with a broader EU funding context, > whereby the continued support of EU funds is moving towards requiring > evidence of positive results and impacts.

Strategic uncertainties

There are multiple uncertainties that may have a significant impact on the ECCCH in this area. These uncertainties primarily involve the following concerns:

- Program Funding: It is still unknown which types of instruments will have the most significance and what response will be made towards those instruments in terms of the supply of resources, as well, as the situations where infrastructures (like ECCCH) are to be supported.

- Cost Trajectory for Digital Services: The cost of cloud computing and data center infrastructure will be highly variable. The uncertainty in the magnitude and direction of expenses associated with these resources over time will have a serious impact on how ECCCH will function as an operational entity.

- Balance between Openness and Commercial Viability: The uncertainty surrounding the ability for ECCCH to continue to provide open, inclusive access while still being able to afford to keep operating will be a concern for ECCCH if the availability of funds will decrease, and/or if the availability of funds and/or resources to support the operation of ECCCH becomes more competitive and/or conditional on a return on investment to the financial supporter.

B.3.3 Social Dimension

Context and key drivers

Institutional capacity is the crucial element to be addressed from a social perspective for the ECCCH. That includes uneven distribution of digital competencies throughout the cultural heritage sector, changing expectations about how the public will participate in and access, and how relevant these infrastructures will be to contemporary society.

Multiple causes provide impetus for these challenges:

1. First is that there is a disparity between organisations with strong digital teams and those that do not. Organisations with a strong digital focus and good data management may employ many staff with significant technical and data skills, whereas smaller organisations may rely on a small percentage of staff with limited technical capabilities and resources. All parties involved have stated that a primary reason why organisations cannot participate in developing advanced digital infrastructures is the lack of dedicated technical positions and data stewarding capabilities. At the European level, digital competencies are referred to as a structural barrier to development, as brought up during the Digital Decade Monitoring Framework report (2020). There continues to be significant skill gaps in the area of advanced digital competencies that reflect the larger policy environment in which cultural heritage organisations will operate in.
2. Second, the growing expectation that cultural heritage organisations are developed to serve as inclusive public goods that increase access for users from varying geographic locations, languages, types of institutions, and user communities shall influence the development of the ECCCH. The ECCCH is being developed to be a collaborative digital commons based on the ECHOES framework. For this reason, there are social expectations from Users with regard to equitable access across multiple geographical locations.
3. A third factor affecting the way heritage experts work as professionals, including how work tasks are performed, is changing professional roles and workflows. Cultural heritage institutions will need to adapt to their organisational structure and create new hybrid types of positions (i.e. mixes of different types of roles) that require skills in the use of digital literacy and data management, in addition to the specialised knowledge of their field.
4. A fourth driver to adoption is the need for both trust and legitimacy. Professionals working in cultural heritage will increasingly require transparency, accountability and explainability when using digital technologies and AI-enabled tools (e.g. decision support systems and automated analysis) that can impact the interpretation, accessibility and or representation of cultural heritage materials.

Implications for ECCCH

- **There are different ways to monitor how institutions participate based on readiness rather than just having the right resources.** Which institutions in the future will be using the ECCCH will ultimately depend on their overall level of readiness to provide the necessary capacity for having the ability to use the services. The fragmentation of participation, without having adequate supportive mechanisms for increasing capacity in all of the necessary skills, talents, and experience, will remain in effect until the institutions can receive those supportive mechanisms.
- **There should be a component within the delivery of ECCCH services that includes organisational capacity building activities as a core functioning layer of the service.** The core components of ECCCH services, such as training, onboarding, documentation, and possibly also having an organised intermediary layer, will be considered as required functions and become integral to the delivery of ECCCH services rather than optional functions.
- **There needs to be means of operationalising inclusion, which will influence design and governance, to ensure that the ECCCH operates as a digital commons of Europe.** Governance, funding models, service design, and the technical aspects of the ECCCH must be designed to actively reduce the imposition of barriers towards participation that may create unequal conditions relative to other institutions. In order to successfully support an organisational medium to long term transformation in their professional practices relative to cultural heritage, ECCCH will contribute positively to the ongoing transformation that cultural heritage professionals will need to undertake as a result of the influence of digital and AI-enabled services.
- **Trust-based activities need to be considered as part of the service design of ECCCH.** Successful adoption of ECCCH services will be reliant on having transparent, accountable, and easily explained digital and AI-enabled services as the determinants of the level of trust that institutions will have in using ECCCH services.

Strategic uncertainties

- Will digital capacity gaps narrow or widen across the sector?

It remains uncertain whether investment in digital infrastructures and skills will reduce inequalities or whether increasing technological complexity may widen participation gaps.

- Which capacity-building models will be sustainable at scale?

The effectiveness of different support models (training, peer learning, embedded support roles, shared services) remains uncertain and will likely evolve over time.

- How will professional roles evolve in response to AI and data-driven workflows?

The pace and direction of workforce transformation across cultural heritage institutions remains uncertain and will depend on technological, regulatory, and funding developments.

B.3.4 Technological Dimension

Context and key drivers

The ways in which ECCCH is affected by the technological environment are constantly evolving. The data infrastructure for cultural heritage research and collaboration is evolving rapidly with technology such as artificial intelligence, digital modelling technologies and distributed computing architectures. These new technologies present many opportunities for researching and collaborating on cultural heritage but create new levels of complexity, governance needs and sustainability issues.

Clearly, one of the primary factors is the acceleration with which AI enabled tools and data driven workflows are being adopted throughout the research and innovation ecosystem. AI is allowing researchers in cultural heritage to perform new types of analysis, automatically enrich metadata, visualise their findings in new ways and integrate large volumes of data from multiple sources. While these advances create new opportunities for cultural heritage researchers, they also create a dependency on compute intensive infrastructure and highly specialised technical expertise.

Another significant factor shaping the ECCCH's technological landscape is the movement toward a distributed and federated digital infrastructure. As digital repositories continue to evolve, the future digital infrastructure will require that they extend beyond the centralised repository model and rely instead on independent and interoperable services, one or more shared data layers, and a distributed processing model. The evolution of digital infrastructure is aligned with the ECCCH vision for a collaborative European digital environment where knowledge resources can be shared and created collaboratively.

The final driver of change is the need to create infrastructure that is efficient and sustainable. With the ongoing evolution of digital infrastructure, a number of significant design constraints will have to be addressed, such as limitations related to energy

consumption, data storage optimisation and compute performance. The partners involved in the project recognised the importance of reducing unnecessary data storage and enabling more efficient forms of data processing to provide the requisite reliability, security and cost effectiveness for future cultural heritage digital infrastructure. This topic considers how technology will be sovereign when using it as an external commercial provider, such as a long-term risk caused by cost volatility, vendor lock-in and limited strategic autonomy due to the use of such solutions for European public digital commons.

Technological development is becoming more closely connected to regulations, e.g., AI governance, data protection and digital security are now affecting and being included into the design of a solution as part of the solution's initial phase.

Implications for ECCCH

- The ECCCH architecture should enable modular evolution and interoperability: In light of the rapid pace of technological development, the ECCCH architecture should focus on developing modular services and open standards for interoperable systems, allowing future connection with new tools and services.
- Technology choices must be balanced between supporting innovation and ensuring ongoing operational viability; The ECCCH will have to balance advanced capabilities (e.g., AI services, better processing) against cost, energy use, and increasing the complexity of operations.
- Infrastructure design should reduce the risk of structural dependency; Technical and procurement strategies should attempt to limit the risk of being locked into suppliers, thereby promoting long-term independence from third-party suppliers of core services and data layers.
- Regulatory compliance will influence infrastructure design decisions; Technical architecture decisions will increasingly be shaped by security, data governance, and AI regulations, thus making compliance part of the technical architecture decision rather than a downstream consideration.
- ECCCH will be a potential driver of industry standards and technical alignment across the cultural heritage sector; As a European shared infrastructure, it is likely that ECCCH may serve as the model in terms of technical standards and service integration practices across the ecosystem of cultural heritage.

Strategic uncertainties

- Pace of technological change and service obsolescence risk Rapid evolution of AI and data technologies may shorten service lifecycles and require continuous infrastructure adaptation.

- Future availability and cost of compute-intensive technologies Energy costs, hardware supply chains, and market concentration may affect the affordability of advanced processing services.
- Balance between openness and security requirements Increasing cybersecurity and regulatory requirements may introduce tensions with openness and accessibility objectives.

B.3.5 Legal Dimension

Context and key drivers

ECCCH is operating in a legal environment that is conditioned by the interaction of a range of regulatory and rights frameworks regarding how data about cultural heritage can be created, accessed, shared, enriched and reused across borders. Legal conditions are not peripheral for the collaborative cloud that intended to function as European digital commons; they have a direct impact on how infrastructure is designed, how governance arrangements are developed, what thresholds there are for participating in the collaborative cloud and how long the collaborative cloud will be sustainable.

The complexity of the structural copyright and IPR regimes that affect the creation of cultural heritage content is one of the main drivers of the above-defined environments, as different nation-states, interpreters of laws and different institutions define and apply copyright laws and other legal definitions in variable ways. Partners have indicated that licensing requirements frequently determine whether data can be made widely accessible and that legal fragmentation creates barriers to the reuse of data across borders.

The tension between the aspirations for open access and the constraints of the law is the second major driver. Partners expressed an interest in determining if Open Data should be treated as a primary goal or a secondary goal, indicating that the factors of openness are not only technical or ethical choices but also related to the laws and governance that help define the collaborative cloud.

A third driver involves legal questions related to AI-enabled services and processing through automation's effect on those activities. Development of EHCCG's is taking place in an environment where AI governance is being increasingly defined at the EU level, although partners are also aware of continuing confusion regarding accountability, liability and compliance in contexts where distributed systems are being developed.

The fourth driver is challenges in assigning liability/responsibility within the ECCCG, given the multiple parties (data providers, service providers, consumers/users, governance

units) involved in the overall ecosystem. As a result, partners are not sure who will have responsibility for which tools and information cross organisational borders.

Lastly, legal restrictions affect access to participate. If obligations to comply are cumbersome or expensive to comply, smaller organisations may face additional hurdles even before attempting to participate in the EHCCG.

Implications for ECCCH

- **Licensing and the management of rights should be treated as core components of infrastructure.** ECCCH will need to create a way for them to manage rights, records of licensing and conditions under which they provide access for the data at a scale that will work. If no method is developed, ECCCH will have a structural barrier to making data available for reuse.
- **To achieve openness, you need to have both the legal operating design and the policy statement.** If ECCCH's goal is to provide support for open cooperation, there must be a legal mechanism to provide access to various levels of openness (i.e., open, limited, and controlled access). In addition, there will need to be governance rules about the circumstances that dictate that restrictions be applied and why.
- **There will be a need for a clear allocation of responsibility to support institutions with liability and support them in participating.** If there is uncertainty regarding who has responsibility for compliance and therefore how to mitigate potential damages stemming from the misuse or downstream effects, this can create an unwillingness for organisations to participate in the process of collaboration resulting in increased risk aversion. ECCCH will need to establish explicit models for assigning responsibility and maintain a system of practical risk management.
- **ECCCH will be able to provide support for compliance and will support participation by creating low barriers to entry for smaller organisations.** To provide low barriers to entry and to support compliance efforts, ECCCH will need to provide shared legal information (tools, templates, guidance) that supports community members in developing and supporting the effective use of e.g., model licenses, recommended clauses or templates, or compliance checklists. This information will be part of onboarding and service delivery.
- **Legal interoperability will have a large impact on providing a scalable foundation for organisations collaborating across borders.** For ECCCH to provide support for pan-European collaboration, it must be able to effectively reduce inter-organisational friction created by differences in the laws/regs

governing reuse and creation of derivations that result from the differing cultural frameworks of EU member states.

Strategic uncertainties

- **To what extent can legal harmonisation be effectively advanced?** Despite having common templates or guidance, it is still uncertain how far the ECCCH will be able to reduce fragmentation in various practices and interpretations of rights across different institutions and Member States (MSs).
- **How will the ECCCH share and distribute (potentially) responsibility and liability within the ECCCH ecosystem?** One of the major uncertainties regarding the development of the ECCCH concerns how to share responsibilities among all governing bodies (e.g., the European Commission), service providers, data providers, and end users, especially if AI tools create new outputs or interpretations.
- **What will be the boundary of the ECCCH with respect to openness and legal risk containment?** At what point will open access and restrictive access reach the appropriate balance? This will depend on evolving practice, individual stakeholder risk appetites, and individual compliance responsibility (that has yet to be resolved among stakeholders)

B.3.6 Environmental Dimension

Context and key drivers

The environmental context for ECCCH has two converging dynamics: an increase in climate-related risks that threaten cultural heritage assets and institutions, and an increase in expectations for digital infrastructure to show credible environmental accountability.

The first driver is an increased rate of climate-related impacts across Europe that continue to threaten cultural heritage through flooding, heat waves, drought, wildfires, coastal hazards, and cascading infrastructure failures. These hazards affect not only monuments and collections but also surrounding local communities as well as the sociocultural systems that support the preservation of intangible heritage. Climate change is increasingly framed as a systemic risk that requires a coordinated approach to adapt and build resilience in multiple sectors within EU policy and evidence of this will continue to grow.

The second driver is an increase in scrutiny on digital infrastructure’s environmental footprint. Data centres, storage, and AI-based computing are associated with high

energy usage and emissions; therefore, there is heightened pressure on the industry to substantiate any sustainability claims made with measurable documentation. Partners noted that by not tracking environmental performance against valid indicators, there are reputational and strategic risks through "greenwashing".

The third driver is the level of availability and reliability of transparency from digital infrastructure providers regarding their environmental performance. Partners raised uncertainty as to the ability of suppliers to meet the needs for the type of data required to provide credible governance of sustainability.

A fourth driver concerns how the growing emphasis on sustainability criteria will be used when making technology purchasing and designing infrastructure decisions (through the inputs from the members of the Consortium). In making procurement decisions, it is necessary for partners to include sustainability metrics to be incorporated within the process, such as when selecting service provider/s or computer solutions.

Implications for ECCCH

The ECCCH should be designed to help protect cultural heritage from climate change by incorporating all aspects of risk-informed practice into Heritage Conservation Planning. Systems of documentation, monitoring data, modelling climate change impacts on heritage and the sharing of that knowledge must happen in a more systematic and collaborative manner. Given the need to prioritise services and interoperability pathways that allow institutions to respond to climate change pressures in an operation-based way, the services offered through ECCCH must align with these administrative procedures.

- **There must be measurable and governance-linked environmental sustainability;** In order to ensure that environmental sustainability can be evidenced and audited over time, ECCCH should likely include sustainability KPIs and reporting frameworks that will provide for the credible tracking of the organisation's performance in terms of its environmental impact. The ECCCH partners specifically requested indicators (including a life cycle approach) that would serve as a safeguard against unsupported claims.
- **Provider selection & architecture decisions become sustainability decisions;** Sustainability criteria should be used to evaluate infrastructure decisions (storage strategies, processing architecture, etc., as well as the provider selected), rather than cost & performance alone. This means that sustainability considerations must be incorporated into procurement and technical governance processes in all contracts.

- **Sustainability requirements may provide barriers to participation for smaller institutions unless mitigated;** If sustainability requirements become very demanding (i.e., complex reporting procedures or higher technical barriers), smaller institutions may be faced with even more barriers to participation than they already have. The ECCCH should look to mitigate this risk through shared tools & support mechanisms.

Strategic uncertainties

- **Can sustained governance provide credibility without the provision of complete and accurate transparency by suppliers?** There is considerable uncertainty regarding whether suppliers will provide sufficient detail to ECCCH about their environmental performance (in order to provide for evaluation and accountability).
- **What trade-offs will ECCCH make between developing energy-required technology innovations and limiting these same technologies to meet environmental or sustainability limits?** AI-enabled services along with different technologies used for providing services might require a significant amount of energy to develop and operate. Whether or not ECCCH will build a positive reputation for their services and meet the stringent sustainability targets will depend on emerging technologies and the choices made about how to govern these innovations.
- **How rapidly will evidence of climate risk result in tangible changes in operating practices for heritage organisations such as libraries, museums, and galleries?** Although the risk that climate presents to organisations is being recognised more than ever, the pace at which these organisations will utilise risk-based strategies for managing climate-related risks could vary significantly, as well as the potential impact that ECCCH's infrastructure and services may have on accelerating the adoption of climate risk-based strategies.

Cross-dimension Synthesis

Interactions across PESTLE dimensions -

PESTLE Analysis identifies that the external environment that determines the ECCCH's implementation is very complex, consisting of connected, interdependent factors. Examples of these factors would be: Political priorities, funding, and regulatory conditions influencing the ability to introduce technological innovations; technological developments affect the legal and ethical frameworks in which technology must fit; social capacity constraints limit the ability to adopt technological innovations; and the global

need for environmental sustainability will increasingly influence the design and construction of infrastructure.

The first cross-cutting dynamic relates to the intersection of the digital infrastructure policy and the digital ecosystem of the sector, with political priorities that are tied to digital sovereignty shaping the types of technology architecture and governance models that are selected as part of the ECCCH. In doing so, it establishes the ECCCH's positioning within the broader landscape of Europe's digital public infrastructure.

Second, a cross-cutting dynamic is the nexus of innovation and regulations. That is, as AI-enabled services and data-rich processes are rolling out, regulatory frameworks that govern AI, data protection, and digital governance are also being created, meaning that technological progress is becoming more legally conditioned.

Third, a systemic dynamic is the effect of economic sustainability and social inclusion. Funding models, costs, and methods for procuring ECCCH services shape who can access them. Therefore, economic design choices will also affect social outcomes.

Fourth, an increasing relationship is being built between technological scalability and environmental accountability. As ECCCH services expand, the sustainability of the built infrastructure to deliver those services becomes less a matter of optimising technology, and more a matter of governance.

Lastly, the fifth cross-cutting dynamic is about trust and legitimacy: trust is created at the intersection of legal compliance, technological transparency, governance inclusiveness, and political legitimacy; this multidimensional aspect of trust is one of the systemic features that underpins the ECCCH's viability as an entity.

Cross-cutting strategic tensions

The PESTLE analysis reveals several structural tensions ECCCH will likely need to navigate over time:

- **Openness vs control**
ECCCH is envisioned as a collaborative digital commons, but must also manage legal, security, and governance constraints.
- **Innovation speed vs regulatory and ethical assurance**
Rapid technology adoption can conflict with compliance timelines and governance maturity.
- **Infrastructure performance vs environmental footprint**
Advanced digital services may increase compute demand and energy use.

- **Financial sustainability vs inclusiveness**
Long-term funding models may require cost recovery mechanisms that risk excluding smaller institutions.
- **European coordination vs national diversity**
ECCCH must operate across heterogeneous legal, policy, and institutional contexts.

System-level strategic questions for ECCCH

The information provided using PESTLE indicates a set of high-level strategic governance/design questions for the ECCCH:

- What are some ways to make sure that ECCCH aligns with European strategic infrastructures but is still open, accountable, and grounded in community input?
- How can ECCCH put digital/information innovation that is both compliant with regulations and considered trustworthy into practice without impeding experimentation/fostering adoption?
- What governance-funding models will allow ECCCH to sustain operations over the long run, but not create an unequal playing field?
- What steps can ECCCH take to promote climate change resilience for cultural heritage while ensuring that the digital work is environmentally responsible?
- How can ECCCH retain confidence from other constituents (institutions, nations, professionals) in the context of a wholly distributed digital environment?

Strategic outlook

Taken together, the PESTLE analysis suggests that ECCCH is emerging at the intersection of major structural transformations affecting Europe's knowledge infrastructures. The long-term success of ECCCH will depend on its ability to function simultaneously as a technological platform, a governance system, and a trusted collaborative environment capable of adapting to evolving policy, economic, social, legal, technological, and environmental conditions.

Conclusion and Strategic Recommendations

Conclusion

This analysis has conducted a foresight study of the external environment in which the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) will develop through the use of a PESTLE analysis with the intent of highlighting the structural forces that will impact the evolution of ECCCH throughout the next ten years.

Through all areas of the PESTLE analysis, ECCCH is being created in a context where digital infrastructure is now considered as a strategic asset, where regulatory frameworks governing data and artificial intelligence are continuing to evolve, where risks to climate are increasing, and where public expectations of transparency, inclusion and measurable impact are increasing. These parameters all give further support to the premise that ECCCH is not simply a technical platform, but that it will serve as a long-term, collaborative European infrastructure, which will sit at the intersection of research, public policy and societal value creation.

ECHOES is explicitly framing ECCCH as a digitally sustainable European commons, which will be provided with long-term governance and legal frameworks that will outlive the funded project duration. The long-term ambition of ECCCH necessitates strategic decisions concerning its infrastructure architecture, governance model, participation mechanisms and sustainability pathways early in the process.

The PESTLE analysis demonstrates that ECCCH will be developed in a highly interdependent environment, whereby political factors will affect funding conditions, technological considerations will impact legal obligations, economic factors will create frameworks for inclusion, and environmental factors will increasingly affect the governance of infrastructure.

Strategic recommendations for ECCCH development -

1. **Integrate long-term sustainability into core infrastructure design from the outset;** ECCCH should develop a clear transition pathway from project funding to durable operations, including governance arrangements, cost models, and reinvestment mechanisms. Sustainability should be treated as a strategic design parameter rather than a downstream operational challenge. Embed compliance, trust, and transparency as infrastructure-level functions; Legal compliance, trustworthy AI governance, and transparency should be embedded in ECCCH architecture, service design, and governance models. This includes clear responsibility allocation, licensing pathways, and compliance support mechanisms for participating institutions.
2. **Treat capacity-building and participation enablement as core ECCCH service layers;** To function as a European digital commons, ECCCH will need structured onboarding pathways, shared support services, and capacity-building mechanisms embedded into infrastructure operations. Without this, participation risks remaining uneven across the sector.
3. **Align ECCCH with broader European digital and research infrastructure priorities;** Positioning ECCCH within European strategic infrastructure narratives

(digital sovereignty, secure data ecosystems, knowledge infrastructures) will likely be critical for long-term political and financial support.

4. **Develop credible environmental accountability frameworks for ECCCH operations;** ECCCH should define measurable sustainability indicators, ensure provider transparency, and integrate sustainability criteria into procurement and technical governance decisions to avoid reputational and operational risks.
5. **Anticipate and manage trade-offs between openness, security, and compliance;** ECCCH governance will need to define clear principles and operational mechanisms for balancing openness and reuse with legal, security, and risk-management constraints.
6. **Prioritise interoperability and modular infrastructure design to support long-term adaptability;** Given the pace of technological evolution, ECCCH should prioritise modularity, open standards, and service interoperability to reduce obsolescence risks and enable gradual evolution.
7. **Strengthen ECCCH’s ability to demonstrate societal and research value through impact evidence;** Developing a clear impact logic and evidence framework will likely be essential for long-term funding continuity and political legitimacy in a competitive public investment landscape.

Final outlook

In looking at their opportunity for establishing a new generation of European collaborative digital infrastructure for cultural heritage, ECCCH has the potential to be successful in its long-term vision through the combination of technological innovation with governance maturity; legal robustness; social inclusion; environmental responsibility; and economic sustainability.

Should these various dimensions be integrated together, ECCCH will have the capacity to serve as a foundational pillar within the overall European knowledge infrastructure ecosystem and a reference model for use by research and heritage communities as they engage in collaborative digital commons efforts.

Annex C: Glossary

The following glossary provides concise definitions of key terms used in this SRIA. Where available, definitions are aligned with the ECHOES WP4 shared vocabulary (SKOS-based controlled vocabulary).

Collaborative Cloud — A federated digital infrastructure that provides shared tools, services, and storage for collaborative research and knowledge production in the cultural heritage domain. In this document, the term refers specifically to the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH).

Digital Asset — Any digital object or resource that represents, documents, or relates to a cultural heritage entity, including digitised images, 3D models, textual records, audiovisual materials, and associated metadata.

Digital Commons — A new generation of semantically rich, collectively produced digital resources encompassing tangible heritage objects, archival records, library collections, intangible cultural expressions, and born-digital assets. Digital Commons are governed by shared rules and sustained through community participation.

Digital Continuum — The seamless integration of physical and digital dimensions of cultural heritage, enabling continuous interaction between tangible objects and their digital representations across the full lifecycle of documentation, research, conservation, and public engagement.

ECCCH Integration Task Force (EITF) — A cross-project coordination body that brings together the ECHOES consortium with related Horizon Europe projects (Sister Projects) to ensure alignment, avoid duplication, and foster interoperability in the development of the ECCCH.

FAIR Principles — A set of guiding principles to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Originally articulated for scientific data management, they are central to the ECCCH's approach to digital heritage.

Federation — An architectural model in which distributed, autonomous nodes (institutions, repositories, services) interconnect through shared protocols and standards, enabling resource sharing and interoperability without requiring centralisation.

Heritage Digital Twin (HDT) — A comprehensive, dynamic, and semantically structured digital representation of a cultural heritage entity (object, building, site, or landscape) that integrates multi-layered data from diverse disciplines and sources, enabling

continuous enrichment through collaborative research. Described by the Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (HDTO).

Knowledge Base — A structured, queryable repository of interconnected knowledge derived from Heritage Digital Twins and research activities within the ECCCH, designed to support semantic search, reasoning, and knowledge discovery across heritage domains.

Living Building Blocks — Modular, reusable software components and services developed within the ECHOES project that can be independently deployed, updated, and combined to build applications and workflows on the ECCCH platform.

Ontology — A formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualisation. In the ECCCH context, ontologies such as CIDOC-CRM and HDTO provide the semantic frameworks for structuring and interlinking heritage data across institutions and domains.

Paradata — Documentation of the processes, methodologies, decisions, and interpretive choices involved in creating digital representations of cultural heritage. Paradata ensures transparency and scholarly accountability in digital heritage workflows.

PESTEL Analysis — A strategic foresight framework that examines Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal factors shaping the external operating environment of an organisation or initiative.

Priority Area — One of the three main strategic domains structuring the SRIA's research and innovation recommendations. Each Priority Area groups related Core Themes and is linked to specific R&I Principles and measurable KPIs.

Sister Projects — Horizon Europe projects funded under the same or related calls as ECHOES, which contribute to the development of the ECCCH through complementary research, tools, or services. Coordination with Sister Projects is facilitated through the EITF.

SRIA (Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda) — A strategic document that defines the long-term research and innovation priorities, governance principles, and implementation roadmap for a research infrastructure. This document constitutes the SRIA for the ECCCH.

References

Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas

ARCHE Consortium (2025). ARCHE SRIA and its Synthesis. Alliance for Research on Cultural Heritage in Europe. Deliverable D2.6. Available at: <https://www.heritageresearch-hub.eu/>

EOSC Association (2024). Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Version 1.3. Available at: <https://eosc.eu/sria-mar/>

JPI Cultural Heritage (2020). Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda. Available at: <https://www.heritageresearch-hub.eu/>

Policy Documents and Position Papers

Demetrescu, E., Cano, E., Goulet, A.-M., Barbot, M. S., Calcerano, F., De Luca, L., Garcia, J., Pedrazzi, T., & Saintenoy, T. (2025). Cultural Heritage Position paper - European research challenges: CNR, CNRS, CSIC Humanities & Social Sciences Scientific perspectives. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17533725>

JPI Cultural Heritage and JPI Climate (2022). White Paper: Cultural Heritage and Climate Change – New Challenges and Perspectives for Research.

European Commission (2024). Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025-2027.

ECHOES Project Internal Documents

Demetrescu, E. (2025). A Vision on the Heritage Cloud. Presentation at ECHOES General Assembly, Antwerpen, September 25th, 2025.

European Framework Documents

Council of the European Union (2014). Council conclusions of 21 May 2014 on cultural heritage as a strategic resource for a sustainable Europe (2014/C 183/08).

European Commission (2019). The European Green Deal. COM(2019) 640 final.

European Commission (2022). Strengthening cultural heritage resilience for climate change – Where the European Green Deal meets cultural heritage.

EU Regulations

Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act). Official Journal of the European Union L, 2023/2854, 22.12.2023.

Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (AI Act). Official Journal of the European Union L, 2024/1689, 12.7.2024.

Regulation (EU) 2022/868 on European data governance (Data Governance Act). Official Journal of the European Union L 152, 3.6.2022.

Directive (EU) 2019/1024 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (Open Data Directive). Official Journal of the European Union L 172, 26.6.2019.

EU Policy Frameworks for Cultural Heritage

Commission Recommendation (EU) 2021/1970 on a common European data space for cultural heritage. Official Journal of the European Union L 401, 12.11.2021.

European Commission (2025). A Culture Compass for Europe. Brussels.

European Commission (2025). The Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage — Strategy 2025–2030.

Digital Infrastructure Frameworks

European Commission (2020). A European strategy for data. COM(2020) 66 final.

International Heritage Frameworks

UNESCO (2003). Charter on the Preservation of the Digital Heritage.

Council of Europe (2005). Framework Convention on the Value of Cultural Heritage for Society (Faro Convention). CETS 199.

ESFRI (2024). Working Group on Monitoring and Evaluation: Monitoring of Research Infrastructures Performance.